

1 **Sensitisation of OSL Signals in Quartz and Provenance Implications: Insights from Multi-**
2 **Spectroscopic Analysis of Quartz from Multiple Geological Settings**

3 **Monika Devi^{1*}, Serban-Constantin Grecu^{1,2}, Zsejke-Réka Tóth¹, Daniela Constantin¹, Daniela**
4 **Brezeanu^{1,2}, Anca Barla³, Ion Nesterovschi⁴, Simona Cinta-Pinzaru⁴, Mihai N. Ducea^{3,5},**
5 **Stephen J. Mojzsis^{6,7}, Alida Timar-Gabor^{1,2*}**

6 ¹Interdisciplinary Research Institute on Bio-Nano-Sciences, Babes-Bolyai University, Treboniu
7 Laurian 42, 400271 Cluj-Napoca, Romania

8 ²Faculty of Environmental Science and Engineering, Babes-Bolyai University, Fântânele 30,
9 400535 Cluj-Napoca, Romania

10 ³Department of Geosciences, University of Arizona, 1040 E. 4th Street, AZ, 85721 Tucson, AZ,
11 USA

12 ⁴Faculty of Physics, Babes-Bolyai University, Strada Mihail Kogălniceanu 1, 400347 Cluj-Napoca,
13 Romania

14 ⁵Faculty of Geology and Geophysics, University of Bucharest, Blvd. Bălcescu 1, 010041
15 Bucharest, Romania

16 ⁶HUN-REN Research Centre for Astronomy and Earth Sciences (CSFK) MTA Centre of Excellence
17 Konkoly-Thege Miklós út 15-17, 1121 Budapest, Hungary

18 ⁷Bavarian Research Institute of Experimental Geochemistry and Geophysics (BGI), University of
19 Bayreuth, Universitätsstraße 30, 95447 Bayreuth, Germany ation for author 1.

20 Corresponding author: Monika Devi (monika.devi@ubbcluj.ro) and Alida Timar-Gabor
21 (alida.timar@ubbcluj.ro)

22 **Key Points:**

- 23 • Defects in quartz from granites, volcanic, metamorphic rocks, sandstones, and
24 sediments are studied using multiple spectroscopic methods.
- 25 • Quartz from different rocks shows variable light sensitivity linked to inherited defects
26 and metal impurities.
- 27 • Titanium, lithium impurities and their associated paramagnetic centres in source rocks
28 strongly influence quartz luminescence sensitivity.

29 **Abstract**

30 Quartz optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) sensitivity and electron spin resonance (ESR)
31 signals have been empirically proposed as indicators for sediment provenance. OSL sensitivity is
32 defined as luminescence produced per unit dose (Gray: Gy) per unit mass (mg). The
33 mechanisms driving OSL sensitization of quartz grain after detachment from source rocks
34 remain an open question in the luminescence community. Most previous work has focused
35 solely on sink sediments, while recent studies highlight the role of lattice defects in the source
36 rocks in the OSL sensitisation process.

37 The present study investigates the OSL sensitization by dosing and bleaching of quartz from
38 diverse rocks, including granites, sandstones, volcanic rocks, metamorphic rocks, and, in some
39 cases, their derived sediments, with ages ranging from millions to billions of years. We combine
40 thermoluminescence, OSL, ESR, cathodoluminescence (CL) and Raman spectroscopy, with
41 geochemical data obtained through laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass
42 spectrometry (LA-ICPMS). Quartzes that showed OSL sensitisation following repeated cycles of
43 laboratory dosing and bleaching exhibited the $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$ electron centre in ESR, had notably
44 high concentration of titanium and lithium impurities and had high blue emission in SEM-CL.
45 Samples lacking these centres did not show any laboratory OSL sensitisation. We find a strong
46 correlation of the degree of laboratory OSL sensitisation with the $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$ electron centre and
47 saturated $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ hole centre from ESR signal, and the titanium and lithium concentrations
48 measured by LA-ICPMS. Our data reinforce the idea that the potential for OSL sensitisation
49 originates from specific lattice defect structures acquired by quartz during crystallisation.

50 **Plain Language Summary**

51 Quartz, one of Earth's most common minerals, preserves a hidden record of its past. When
52 exposed to sunlight or radiation, it emits light signals that reveal when sediments were last
53 buried. This luminescence dating method helps reconstruct past landscapes, climate change,
54 and human migration. Quartz grains show variable luminescence signals-some strong and
55 others weak. This variability is used in provenance studies to trace sediment sources, but its
56 cause remains an open question in the luminescence community. Our study explores this
57 question by examining quartz from various rocks and sediments around the world. Using a
58 combination of luminescence, electron spin resonance, cathodoluminescence, and chemical
59 analyses, we report that the ability of quartz to sensitise (produce stronger light signals after
60 exposure) depends on tiny imperfections in its crystal structure. In particular, quartz grains rich
61 in titanium and lithium, and showing associated paramagnetic defect, consistently produced
62 strong increase of signals, while others did not. These findings show that the story of
63 landscapes recorded in sediments begins deep in the rocks themselves. By linking luminescence
64 behaviour to rock defects, we can improve the reliability of dating methods and open new
65 pathways for tracing sediment sources across Earth's surface.

66 **1 Introduction**

67 The aim of provenance studies is to determine the origin and history of sediments or rocks by
68 capturing their mineralogical, geochemical, and textural characteristics through analysis. This
69 approach offers insights necessary for the reconstruction of past geological processes, sediment

70 transport pathways, and tectonic processes. In sedimentary basins, provenance analysis is used
71 for reconstructing sediment routing systems, i.e., sediment fingerprinting and sediment
72 budgeting (Clift, 2006; Guzmán et al., 2013; Koiter et al., 2013; Goswami et al., 2024; Parida et
73 al., 2025). Most provenance studies focus on accessory minerals. A common method used in
74 provenance studies is the analysis of detrital zircon U-Pb age spectra to trace sediment sources
75 (Gehrels, 2014). These same studies frequently apply low-temperature thermochronologic
76 methods to minerals such as apatite, titanite, and zircon (e.g., fission track and U-Th/He dating;
77 Reiners, 2005), or mica $^{40-39}\text{Ar}$ geochronology (e.g., Gemignani et al., 2017). By definition, these
78 accessory minerals represent only a small fraction of the total sediment load and the relative
79 abundances of these minerals may not reflect the actual sediment mass. This is owing to the
80 fact that the abundance of many accessory minerals is highly dependent upon the detailed
81 origin of various source rocks, sorting, and preferential preservation or destruction (erosion,
82 decomposition) relative to the major mass of sedimentary material (Garzanti et al., 2007;
83 Morton and Hallsworth, 2007; Caracciolo, 2020). Hence, inherent bias is accrued when using
84 accessory minerals in provenance studies.

85 Quartz is the dominant mineral in sand-sized sediments and typically accounts for a large
86 proportion of sand-sized particles (commonly >70%) in many sedimentary systems (Blatt,
87 1987). Its durability and abundance ensures that parent rocks containing quartz are well
88 represented in their daughter sediments through detrital quartz grains (Basu, 1985). It is well
89 established that even the purest quartz crystal contains a vast number of point defects, which
90 may be either intrinsic (e.g., O-vacancies and related defects or Si vacancies) or due to
91 impurities, most often as combination of monovalent (H^+ , Li^+ , and Na^+) and trivalent (Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} ,
92 and B^{3+}) cations (Götze, 2009; Preusser et al., 2009). Some of these defects remain unchanged
93 under local ionizing radiation by $^{235-238}\text{U}$, ^{232}Th and ^{40}K decay intrinsic to the rock and extrinsic
94 effects such as cosmic rays. Other defects can be transformed, generally by charge trapping.
95 During irradiation, electrons and holes generated in the crystal lattice may become trapped at
96 pre-existing defect sites, leading to the formation or modification of paramagnetic and
97 luminescence centres. For example, substitutional impurities such as Al^{3+} in the Si site can
98 capture holes and release the monovalent cations (e.g., $\text{M}^+ = \text{Li}^+$ or H^+) to form $[\text{AlO}_4]^\circ$ hole
99 centres, while Ti-related defects capture electrons and then monovalent cations for the charge
100 compensation forming $[\text{TiO}_4\text{M}^+]^\circ$ electron centres. These point defects in quartz have the
101 capacity to carry petrogenetic information in that their modifications can provide information
102 on the type and age of the host rock, weathering, transport, or recycling in time. Paramagnetic
103 defects in quartz such as E'_1 centres (unpaired electrons at oxygen vacancy sites, $\equiv\text{Si}\cdot$), intrinsic
104 peroxy centres ($\equiv\text{Si}-\text{O}-\text{O}\cdot$), non-bridging oxygen hole centres (NBOHC, $\equiv\text{Si}-\text{O}\cdot$), and various
105 impurity-related complexes involving Aluminium, Titanium, or Germanium (e.g., $[\text{AlO}_4]^\circ$, $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^\circ$,
106 $[\text{GeO}_4\text{Li}^+]^\circ$) can be identified using electron spin resonance (Weil, 2000; Mashkovtsev &
107 Pan, 2013). Additionally, defects such as NBOHCs and oxygen-deficiency centres (ODCs, $\equiv\text{Si}-\text{Si}\equiv$)
108 can be investigated through photoluminescence or cathodoluminescence spectroscopy
109 (Stevens-Kalceff, 2009; Skuja et al., 2020).

110 While the interaction mechanisms of natural radiation with quartz have long been a subject of
111 study (Mackey, 1963; McKeever et al., 1985; Benzid & Timar-Gabor, 2020a, 2020b, 2021), it is
112 still unclear how the defects in sedimentary grains or their precursors inherited from the source
113 rock are influenced by transport and weathering and other factors in the sedimentary systems.

114 Despite this limited knowledge the luminescence sensitivity has been employed as a sediment
115 provenance indicator (**Sawakuchi et al., 2011; Gray et al., 2019**). That is generally defined as
116 the luminescence counts per unit radiation dose (Gray: Gy) per unit mass (mg). The variation in
117 sensitivity is reported for quartz from different origins and hence can be used for provenance
118 studies. Several luminescence signals and ESR related defects in quartz have been used for
119 provenance studies (**Sawakuchi et al., 2011; Jeong and Choi, 2012; Gray et al., 2016; Toyoda et**
120 **al., 2016; Sawakuchi et al., 2018; Gray et al., 2019; del Río et al., 2021; Mineli et al., 2021**).
121 Quartz luminescence sensitivity has been shown to be influenced by a range of geological and
122 environmental processes operating from source to sink systems. **Sawakuchi et al., 2018** and
123 **Tanski et al., 2024** have shown that quartz OSL sensitivity in sediments is dependent on
124 weathering and denudation rates of the parent rock. On the other hand, OSL sensitivity can be
125 modified by thermal events such as heating (**Li, 2002**) and wildfire (**Zhang et al., 2023**) or can
126 depend on erosion and transport distances (e.g., **Pietsch et al., 2008; Fitzsimmons, 2011;**
127 **Sawakuchi et al., 2011; Jeong & Choi, 2012**). Recent studies suggest that OSL sensitivity is
128 influenced by source lithology and crystallisation age (**Alexanderson, 2022; Capaldi et al., 2022;**
129 **Timar-Gabor et al., 2023**). **Constantin et al. (2025)** investigated the relation between the OSL
130 sensitisation of single lithology source rocks and their derived sediments. These authors
131 reported that OSL sensitisation is an effect of the existence of certain defects and impurities in
132 the quartz crystal, such as titanium and germanium inherited from the parent rock.
133 Importantly, only rocks with the presence of these defects showed OSL sensitisation in the
134 laboratory and in nature. The degree of OSL sensitisation reached in nature, however, is
135 significantly higher than that in laboratory experiments designed to reproduce the effect.
136 The present study expands the work of **Constantin et al. (2025)** by investigating relationships
137 between OSL sensitisation by dosing and bleaching, defect centres, and impurity concentrations
138 on quartz from a broader range of lithologies, including granites, sandstones, volcanic rocks and
139 metamorphic rocks and, in some cases, their derived sediments, spanning geological ages from
140 millions (Ma) to billions (Ga) of years. We applied multi-spectroscopic techniques such as TL,
141 OSL, ESR, CL and Raman spectroscopy to study the defects inside the quartz crystals in rocks
142 and these methods were complemented by the results from Laser ablation- inductively coupled
143 plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICPMS) measurements. We find a strong correlation between
144 the degree of OSL sensitisation and the $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$ paramagnetic centre (from ESR), as well as Ti
145 and Li concentrations obtained from LA-ICPMS data. This relationship is further supported by
146 blue emission in CL, attributed to Ti-related defects. Our results show that Ti and Li impurities,
147 along with their associated paramagnetic centres, play a key role in modulating OSL
148 sensitisation in the laboratory during repeated bleaching and dosing cycles. The present study
149 also highlights the important role of Li in the formation of ESR centres such as $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$ and
150 $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ during irradiation, and their contribution to the OSL sensitisation of quartz grains in
151 nature through exposure to radiation and light.

152 **2 Studied samples**

153 A total of nine samples were investigated in this study, three rock and one sediment samples
154 from Arizona (USA), three rock and one sediment sample from Romania, and one rock sample
155 from a sandstone from Western Australia. Out of these samples, two granites and their derived

156 sediments are shared with **Constantin et al. (2025)**. Geological maps and details of the samples
157 are provided in **Figure S1a, b, c and d and Table 1**, respectively.

158 2.1 Arizona samples

159 For this study, the four samples represent both the footwall and the hanging wall of the
160 Catalina detachment system, highlighting the magmatic relationship between plutonic and
161 volcanic rocks, as well as the sedimentary linkage between granite bedrock and derived
162 deposits (**Figure S1a**). These include: (1) a bedrock sample of Oracle Granite (ORACLE) and (2) a
163 bedrock sample of Catalina Granite (CATA G) from the footwall (3) a fluvial sediment sample
164 (CATA-SED MND) derived from Catalina Granite collected approximately 3.5 km downstream
165 from its source, within the modern wash of a tributary of the Oro River, which drains exclusively
166 sediments originating from the Catalina Intrusion, and (4) a sample of A Mountain Rhyolite Tuff
167 (AMV), interpreted as the volcanic equivalent of CATA G-granite, located in the hanging wall.
168 Samples CATA G and CATA-SED MND were previously investigated by **Constantin et al. (2025)**.
169 The Oracle Granite (ORACLE) has a zircon U-Pb crystallisation age of ~1.4 Ga (**Fornash et al.,**
170 **2013**) and an apatite fission track (AFT) age of ~20–23 Ma (**Fayon et al., 2000**). Along with its
171 possible deeper-seated equivalents is considered the primary source of the younger granitoids,
172 except for the Catalina Granite (**Fornash et al., 2013**).

173 The Catalina Granite (CATA G) is a large intrusive body (10-15 km in horizontal diameter)
174 situated in the core of the Catalina detachment system. It represents the plutonic equivalent of
175 a regional Oligocene magmatic flare-up episode and is considered the latest granitic intrusion in
176 the area. U-Pb zircon crystallisation ages of 25-27 Ma (**Ducea et al., 2020**) as well as fission
177 track ages of 28-30 Ma on sphene, 24-29 Ma on zircon and 21-24 Ma on apatite (**Creasy et al.,**
178 **1977**) were reported for granite. The rock is largely unaltered and exhibits well preserved
179 primary mineralogy suggesting minimal post-emplacement deformation (**Figure S2a, b and c**),
180 according to the petrographic analysis.

181 In contrast, A Mountain Rhyolite Tuff, collected from the Sentinel Peak, Tucson Mountains, is
182 the extrusive product of the same magmatic episode, crystallizing during the collapse of the
183 Catalina detachment system. The petrographic analysis showed that AMV is a rhyolitic tuff
184 (**Figure S2d and e**), known as the Tumamoc Tuff (**Guild, 1905; Brown, 1939; Phillips, 1976**). It is
185 characterised by a K-Ar age of ~26-28 Ma (**Bikerman & Damon, 1966**).

186 2.2 Romania

187 Two samples of Albesti granite have been collected from Iezer Mountains in Southern
188 Romanian Carpathians (**Figure S1b, Table 1**). Sample DR1 is an undeformed granite sample
189 while DR2 is its metamorphic equivalent. This sill-like granitoid occurs close to a ductile shear
190 zone (locally named the Bughea shear zone) of presumed Variscan age; the granitoid is exposed
191 as relatively undeformed away from the shear zone (DR1), as well as highly strained into a
192 mylonitic fabric when incorporated into the shear zone (DR2). Samples of Albesti granite have a
193 U-Pb zircon crystallisation age of ~460 Ma (**Medaris Jr et al., 2003**).

194 The granite bedrock sample (RATG 22-06) and its derived sediment (RATG 22-03) from the
195 Retezat Mountains in Southern Romanian Carpathians (**Figure S1c, Table 1**), that has been
196 previously investigated in Constantin et al. (2025) has also been discussed in this study.

197 Sediment sample collection ensured that Retezat granite as a single source rock. The Retezat
198 Mountains comprise part of the Danubian Terrane, which belongs to the Marginal Dacides in
199 the terrane architecture of **Săndulescu (1984)**. Early U-Pb zircon ages on Retezat granitoid
200 yielded a 310 ± 5 Ma age (**Balintoni et al., 2014**). New geochronological data from multiple
201 plutons indicate that the Retezat batholith formed mainly in the earliest Permian, supported by
202 prominent 290-300 Ma detrital age peaks in modern sediments attributed to a Retezat source
203 (**Ducea et al., 2018**). An apatite fission track age of 17 ± 2 Ma on chlorite schist was reported by
204 **Bojar et al., (1998)**.

205 2.3 Western Australia

206 The Jack Hills, situated within the Narryer Gneiss Terrane of the Yilgarn Craton in Western
207 Australia, form an 80-kilometer long, northeast-trending belt of folded and metamorphosed
208 supracrustal rocks including quartzites, conglomerates, banded iron-formations, metapelitic
209 rocks and others (**Figure S1d**). The primary lithology consists of sedimentary siliciclastic rocks,
210 interpreted as alluvial fan-delta deposits. The sequence also includes minor occurrences of
211 mafic/ultramafic rocks and banded iron formations. Overall, the sequence is regarded as
212 granulite gneiss, having experienced multiple deformation phases and several episodes of
213 metamorphism (**Wilde et al., 2001**). This sample documented to contain Hadean zircons,
214 included the oldest known terrestrial material at 4.38 Ga, with a deposition age ~ 3.3 -3.2 Ga
215 (**Mojzsis et al., 2001**).

216 3 Methodology

217 All measurements were carried out on 250–500 μm quartz extracted from the different rock
218 and sediment samples. Standard quartz extraction procedures were used for extracting quartz
219 and details for sample preparation are mentioned in the supplementary material. Out of nine
220 samples, four are from previously published datasets and are re-used here to further
221 investigate relationships between OSL sensitisation, defect centres, and impurity
222 concentrations. Raman spectroscopy was newly performed on these samples. Previous LA-
223 ICPMS data for two granite samples (CATA G and RATG 22-06) included only Li, Ti, and Ge, here,
224 we add new Al data. In addition, new LA-ICPMS data are presented for their derived sediments
225 (CATA-SED MND and RATG 22-03), and their correlation with OSL sensitisation is evaluated.

226 3.1 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), and 227 cathodoluminescence (CL) analyses

228 A ZEISS GeminiSEM 360 Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope, equipped with an
229 integrated Pegasus EDS/EBSD system (Octane Elect Plus, Velocity Plus, PV 5600-EL-PL-Vel-PL)
230 was used for chemical analysis, and a Gatan Monarc Pro spectrometer was used for
231 cathodoluminescence (CL) imaging. Quartz grains extracted from selected samples were
232 mounted on metal stubs using double-sided carbon tape and placed on the microscope's metal
233 stage inside the vacuumed specimen chamber. Each spectral acquisition was conducted with an
234 exposure time of 10 s to optimize signal strength while minimizing beam damage. Other
235 measurement parameters are provided in the supplementary material. Representative SEM
236 images and EDS maps are shown in **Figure S3** and **S4**, respectively.

237 3.2 Luminescence measurements

238 Luminescence analyses were performed using TL/OSL Risø DA-20 readers equipped with a Sr-
239 90/Y-90 beta source delivering a dose rate of 0.08 Gy/s, and an automated detection and
240 stimulation head (DASH; **Lapp et al., 2015**). The optical stimulation system consisted of blue
241 LEDs (470 ± 30 nm, 80 mW/cm²) and IR LEDs (850 ± 30 nm, 300 mW/cm²). OSL and TL emissions
242 were detected using a PDM 9107Q-AP-TTL-03 photomultiplier (sensitive from 160 to 630 nm),
243 fitted with 7.5 mm Hoya U-340 filters (300–390 nm). Aliquots containing approximately 100–
244 300 quartz grains were mounted on 9.7 mm diameter stainless steel discs using silicon oil. All TL
245 glow curves and OSL decay curves presented correspond to a 100 Gy dose.
246 Thermoluminescence (TL) glow curves were recorded at a heating rate of 5 °C/s. OSL
247 sensitisation measurements were conducted in the laboratory by subjecting the samples to 159
248 cycles of 100 Gy beta irradiation, followed by blue LED stimulation for 40 s at 125 °C, and a
249 subsequent 400 s bleach with blue LEDs at the same temperature (see **Table S1** for details). The
250 net OSL signal was calculated using the initial 0.308 seconds of the OSL decay curve, subtracting
251 an early background taken from the 1.538–2.307 s interval. The average of the data from three
252 aliquots is used.

253 3.3 Electron spin resonance

254 Electron spin resonance (ESR) measurements of E'_{1} , peroxy, Al-hole, and Ti centres were
255 conducted using a Bruker EMX Plus X-band spectrometer operating at 9.8 GHz. A high-
256 sensitivity cavity (ER 4119HS Bruker resonator) with an unloaded quality factor of 15,000 and a
257 loaded factor of approximately 7,800 was used for all analyses. All measurements were
258 performed using quartz glass tubes, filled with equal sample volumes to ensure consistency.
259 ESR intensities for all paramagnetic centres are reported for both natural and irradiated
260 (natural+40,000 Gy) doses. To enable inter-sample comparison, ESR intensities were normalised
261 to a mass of 100 mg. In all cases, the defect concentration was quantified using the peak-to-
262 peak amplitude of the ESR signal, which serves as an approximation of defect centre
263 concentration in the samples. For the correlation investigation, ESR intensities of the $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$
264 centre obtained from the natural dose were used. For the $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ centre, ESR intensities
265 corresponding to a high irradiation dose i.e., Natural + 40,000 Gy were used. Detailed ESR
266 measurement parameters for each signal are provided in the supplementary material.

267 3.4 Trace element analysis by laser ablation-inductively coupled plasma mass
268 spectrometry (LA-ICPMS)

269 Trace element concentrations were measured in quartz grains separated from samples using
270 laser ablation quadrupole inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICPMS) at the
271 University of Arizona, following the method described by **Woodhead et al. (2007)**. The quartz
272 grains were cleaned in dilute hydrochloric acid and mounted in 1-inch diameter resin blocks,
273 with 14 individual grains analysed per sample. Standards were co-mounted with the unknowns.
274 Analyses were performed using a Thermo XSeries 2 quadrupole ICPMS (**Rossel et al., 2013**),
275 with laser ablation carried out using a Teledyne Iridia Excimer 193 nm system. A spot size of 35
276 μm was selected to ensure strong signal intensity. Dwell times were optimized using the Iridia

277 system's HDIP software. NIST 610, 612, and 614 were used as calibration standards, with NIST
278 612 serving as the primary standard. The isotope ^{30}Si was measured as an internal standard.

279 3.5 RAMAN spectroscopic analysis

280 The Raman spectra of the quartz samples were acquired using a Renishaw InVia Raman
281 spectrometer coupled with a Leica optical microscope. Excitation was provided by a 785 nm
282 near-infrared (NIR) diode laser. Spectra were collected over the 100 - 1200 cm^{-1} range at a
283 spectral resolution of 1 cm^{-1} , using a 20x objective (NA = 0.35). Each spectrum was recorded
284 with a 1 second exposure time, using a single acquisition at 65 mW laser power. For each
285 sample, the final spectrum represents the average of 100 individual Raman spectra collected
286 from 5 to 8 points on each grain. Spectral pre-processing was performed using Python
287 programming language with Anscombe denoising algorithm and Improved Asymmetric Least
288 Squares (IASLS) method for baseline correction.

289 4 Results

290 4.1 SEM images and EDS analysis

291 The purpose of SEM-images is to show surface morphology and topography of the quartz
292 grains. **Figure S3** presents secondary electron images obtained from SEM for all analysed
293 samples. The imaged grains exhibit surface topography with angular to sub-rounded shapes and
294 relatively smooth surfaces, with minor etching likely resulting from HF treatment during the
295 sample preparation process. These features are consistent with natural quartz morphology. The
296 elemental composition from SEM-EDS of all samples is presented in **Figure S4**. The EDS spectra
297 revealed a clear dominance of silicon (Si) and oxygen (O), which are the principal elements in
298 quartz, along with only minor traces of other elements such as aluminium (Al), titanium (Ti), or
299 iron (Fe), depending on the sample. These findings collectively confirm that the analysed grains
300 are composed predominantly of quartz.

301 4.2 Luminescence characterisation and laboratory OSL sensitisation by dosing and 302 bleaching

303 TL glow curves are presented in **Figure S5**. All samples displayed typical TL peaks at 110 °C, 220
304 °C, 280 °C, 325 °C and 375 °C. Representative OSL decay curves of all samples are shown in
305 **Figure 1**. The OSL decay behaviour varies between samples, as reflected in differing decay rates.
306 ORACLE-granite and JH9902-sandstone display very fast OSL decay, within 1 s of stimulation the
307 signal reaching 13% of the signal recorded (in the first 0.154 s of stimulation). Other samples
308 have a rather fast OSL decay that reaches 30-40% of the initial signal and generally a stable
309 background (CATA-SED MND-sediment, RATG 22-03-sediment and RATG 22-06-granite, DR1-
310 granite) and CATA G-granite, DR2-metamorphosed granite and AMV rhyolite tuff show a
311 relatively slower OSL decay that reach 60-79% of the initial signal.

312 Laboratory OSL sensitisation experiments consisting of 159 cycles of 100 Gy dosing and blue
313 LED exposure produced an increase in OSL sensitivity only in rock and sediment samples from
314 Arizona (AMV-rhyolite, ORACLE-granite, CATA G-granite, CATA-SED MND-sediment) (**Figure 2**).
315 In the case of rock and sediment samples from Australia and Romania (JH9902-sandstone, DR1-

316 granite, DR2-metamorphosed granite, RATG 22-06-granite and RATG 22-03-sediment) the OSL
317 sensitivity was unaffected by dosing and bleaching cycles. As Constantin et al 2025 pointed out,
318 for the CATA-SED MND sediment sample, after a few cycles of dosing and bleaching the initial
319 increase in OSL sensitivity was replaced by OSL de-sensitisation.

320 4.3 Electron Spin Resonance

321 The mass normalised intensities for natural dose of E'_1 , peroxy, Aluminium hole and Titanium
322 electron centres of all samples are shown in **Figure 3**. The mass normalised ESR spectra for
323 natural and natural + 40000 Gy dose of E'_1 , peroxy, Aluminium hole ($[AlO_4]^\ominus$) and Titanium
324 electron centres ($[TiO_4Li^+]^0$) of all samples are shown in **Figure S6** and **S7** and **Table S2**. All
325 samples showed the presence of E'_1 , peroxy, and Aluminium hole centres (**Figure 3**).

326 Significant variations in E'_1 and peroxy centre intensities are observed across the samples. A
327 consistent correlation with $R > 0.94$ is obtained between E'_1 and peroxy signals for both natural
328 dose and high irradiation doses (i.e., Natural + 40 kGy) in all samples (**Figure S8a and 8b**). The
329 concentration of Al-hole centres also varies among samples. Interesting results are obtained for
330 Li compensated Ti electron centres ($[TiO_4Li^+]^0$) that are only detected in Arizona samples AMV-
331 rhyolite, ORACLE-granite, CATA G-granite and CATA-SED MND-sediment, while for samples
332 JH9902-sandstone, DR1-granite, DR2-metamorphosed granite, RATG 22-06-granite and RATG
333 22-03-sediment, no $[TiO_4Li^+]^0$ was detected or below the detection limit of ESR.

334 4.4 SEM-CL

335 The CL emission observed in the studied quartz samples is primarily characterised by two
336 emissions, ~ 650 nm (1.9 eV) and ~ 450 nm (2.7 eV) (**Figure 4**). These emission bands are among
337 the most commonly reported in natural quartz (**Ramseyer et al., 1988; Götze et al., 2001;**
338 **Götze et al., 2015**). The red emission (~ 650 nm (1.9 eV)) is consistently present in all quartz
339 samples (**Figure 4**) and is commonly attributed to non-bridging oxygen hole centres (NBOHCs,
340 $\equiv Si-O\cdot$), which are intrinsic defects involving unpaired electrons localized on oxygen atoms
341 bonded to threefold-coordinated silicon (**Götze et al., 2001; Leeman et al., 2012; Skuja et al.,**
342 **2020**).

343 The blue emission (~ 450 nm, 2.7 eV) is dominant in the Arizona samples: AMV-rhyolite,
344 ORACLE-granite, CATA G-granite and CATA-SED MND-sediment, which are also the samples that
345 got sensitised in the dose and bleaching experiments (**Figure 4a**). On the other hand, the
346 samples that do not get sensitised: JH9902-sandstone, DR1-granite, DR2-metamorphosed
347 granite, RATG 22-06-granite and RATG 22-03-sediment yield a very weak blue emission and a
348 more prominent red emission compared to the blue one (**Figure 4b**). In the present study, we
349 are mainly focussed on the blue emission because of its correlation with Ti impurity (**Götze et**
350 **al., 2024; Fonseca Teixeira et al., 2024**).

351 4.5 LA-ICPMS

352 A summary of trace element concentrations (weighted averages) such as Al, Li, Ge and Ti from
353 LA-ICPMS analysis is shown in **Figure 5** and in **Table S3**. LA-ICPMS data showed variability in the
354 concentrations across the samples as also observed in the ESR analysis. We see a clear
355 distinction between the OSL sensitising and not OSL sensitising samples in terms of Ti and Li

356 concentration. The samples where OSL sensitises, exhibit higher combined concentrations of Ti
357 and Li compared to the samples that do not sensitise. Differences in Ti concentration are
358 observed among samples with distinct geological histories. Higher Ti concentration is found in
359 the rhyolite tuff sample AMV compared to the CATA G granite, whereas a decrease is observed
360 in the DR2 metamorphosed granite relative to the DR1 granite. All samples showed presence of
361 Ge trace element.

362 4.6 RAMAN spectroscopic analysis

363 The average Raman spectra of the quartz samples reveal three characteristic bands at 126, 204,
364 and 464 cm^{-1} (**Figure 6**), consistent with the vibrational modes of crystalline quartz, alongside
365 weaker peaks near 355, 395, and 1161 cm^{-1} (**Krishnan, 1945; Brezeanu et al., 2021; Reynard &**
366 **Zhong, 2023**). Overall, the spectra show no major visual differences, therefore, Lorentzian
367 deconvolution was applied to find small variations and results are shown in **Figure S9**. This
368 analysis highlights some shifts in band positions, intensities and full widths at half maximum
369 (FWHM). Lower peak positions, decreased intensities and broader Raman peaks are associated
370 with increased lattice defects and amorphisation (**Meawad et al., 2025**). In particular, FWHM is
371 a direct indicator of lattice deformation: narrower bands reflect a more ordered, homogeneous
372 crystal lattice with fewer structural defects and lower internal strain, while broader bands
373 indicate increased disorder arising from defects and impurities.

374 For 785 nm stimulation and 128, 206 and 465 cm^{-1} modes AMV-rhyolite presents the lowest
375 band positions, suggesting higher disorder, while ORACLE-granite and JH9902-sandstone exhibit
376 higher positions ($128, 206$ and 465 cm^{-1}) (**Figure S9**), consistent with a more ordered lattice or a
377 result of the compressive stress (**Reynard & Zhong 2023**). These shifts surpass twice the
378 instrumental resolution (1 cm^{-1}) which can be confirmed as statistically significant. FWHM for
379 the 464 cm^{-1} Si-O-Si stretching band position in RATG 22-03-sediment (8.35 cm^{-1}) and CATA-SED
380 MND-sediment (8.12 cm^{-1}) show statistically broader peaks than all other samples, indicating a
381 higher degree of lattice disorder and internal strain in these two samples. The other samples
382 are indistinguishable in FWHM 464 cm^{-1} mode within their respective errors. RATG 22-03-
383 sediment stands out uniquely through its broad 206 cm^{-1} FWHM (15.83 cm^{-1}), indicating
384 pronounced sensitivity of this soft mode to local stress or structural heterogeneity specific to
385 this sample. Additionally, for the 204 cm^{-1} mode, large error bars are observed across all
386 samples, representing its sensitivity as a soft mode to stress and temperature effects (**Morana**
387 **et al., 2023, Reynard & Zhong, 2023**).

388 4.7 Correlation between degree of OSL sensitisation, ESR intensities and trace element 389 concentrations from LA-ICPMS

390 As we observed, only samples containing Ti- and Li-related impurities exhibit OSL sensitisation
391 in the laboratory. Therefore, we investigated the correlation between the degree of OSL
392 sensitisation and both the $[\text{TiO}_4\text{-Li}^+]^0$ centre intensities measured by ESR and the Ti and Li
393 concentrations measured by LA-ICPMS (**Figure 7**). The degree of OSL sensitisation is defined as
394 the ratio between the highest OSL signal ($L_{x,\text{max}}$) to the signal obtained in the first cycle (L_1) of
395 the laboratory sensitisation experiment and values are presented in **Table S4**. A strong positive
396 correlation was observed between the $[\text{TiO}_4\text{-Li}^+]^0$ ESR signal intensity and the degree of OSL

397 sensitisation (**Figure 7a**; Pearson correlation coefficient (r) = 0.96), suggesting that the presence
398 of these paramagnetic centre is closely linked to the OSL sensitisation behaviour of the quartz
399 samples. In addition to these correlations, we observed a strong correlation between degree of
400 sensitisation and saturated $[\text{AlO}_4]^\circ$ (nat+40000 Gy) ESR centre with $r = 0.95$ (**Figure 7b**).
401 Similarly, the concentrations of Li and Ti obtained from LA-ICPMS analysis also showed good
402 correlations with the degree of OSL sensitisation (**Figure 7c and 7d**; $r = 0.95$ and 0.81 ,
403 respectively).

404 Another strong correlation was obtained between Li trace element concentration (LA-ICPMS)
405 and the ESR paramagnetic centres $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^\circ]$ and saturated $[\text{AlO}_4]^\circ$, with r values of 0.89 and
406 0.96 , respectively (**Figure 8a and 8b**). **Figure 8b** shows that the Arizona samples (AMV-rhyolite,
407 ORACLE-granite, CATA G-granite and CATA-SED MND-sediment) containing higher
408 concentration of Li exhibit a pronounced increase in the formation of $[\text{AlO}_4]^\circ$ centres during
409 irradiation compared to the Romanian and Australian samples (JH9902-sandstone, DR1-granite,
410 DR2-metamorphosed granite, RATG 22-06-granite and RATG 22-03-sediment), in which
411 comparatively lower Li concentration were measured. A similar trend is observed for the $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^\circ]$
412 centre in the Arizona samples that display strong $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^\circ]$ ESR signals, whereas this centre
413 is below detection limit in ESR signals in the Romania and Australia samples (**Figure S10**).

414 5 Discussion

415 An increasing number of studies use OSL sensitivity as a proxy for sediment provenance.
416 However, our understanding of the relative roles of intrinsic quartz properties inherited from
417 source rocks versus modifications acquired during sediment transport and environmental
418 exposure remains limited. To date, only a few studies have investigated sensitisation in quartz
419 derived directly from bedrock, and even fewer have focused on granitic sources, despite granite
420 being a major contributor of quartz in sedimentary systems. A limited number of studies have
421 explored laboratory luminescence sensitisation of quartz through repeated dosing and
422 bleaching cycles on rock-derived samples. In this study, we specifically focus on the role of light
423 exposure and irradiation experienced by quartz grains after detachment from the source rock.
424 We extend the findings of **Constantin et al. (2025)**, originally based on two granite samples, to
425 a wider range of lithologies including volcanic, granitic, metamorphic, and sedimentary samples
426 from Arizona, Romania, and Australia. Our results show that intrinsic properties of quartz,
427 particularly Ti and Li-related defects acquired during crystallisation, enable an increase in OSL
428 sensitivity by a factor of ~ 3 to 8 through repeated irradiation and bleaching cycles. This
429 magnitude of laboratory sensitisation is consistent with previous studies. For example, **Mineli**
430 **et al. (2021)** reported similar increases in granite samples from Brazil. **Moska and Murray**
431 **(2006)** observed up to a ~ 7 -fold increase in thermally stable OSL components in sediments
432 recently derived from granitic bedrock, while **Pietsch et al. (2008)** reported increases of ~ 2.5
433 times for multigrain signals and up to ~ 12 times for single-grain quartz from sandstones.
434 Sediment based dose bleach studies also report comparable ranges, such as 1.2 – 3 times (**Zhang**
435 **et al., 2023**), up to ~ 6 times (**Nian et al., 2019**), and ~ 3 times (**McKeever et al., 1996**), indicating
436 that laboratory sensitisation typically results in moderate increases in OSL sensitivity. However,
437 in natural settings, much larger differences are often observed. For instance, **Constantin et al.**
438 **(2025)** reports on short travelled sediments that the Catalina sediment (CATA-SED MND) shows

439 an OSL sensitivity approximately 200 times higher compared to its parent granite, whereas the
440 Retezat sediment (RATG 22-03) shows little difference from its source rock. **Mineli et al. (2021)**
441 observes that the OSL sensitivity in mixed- source sediments is generally higher than that of the
442 possible bedrock samples, with the exception of one short-travelled sediment sample that
443 shows a similar OSL sensitivity as its source rock. Such contrasting behaviours are also reported
444 in other studies and suggest that laboratory irradiation-bleaching cycles alone cannot fully
445 reproduce natural sensitisation processes, there are yet unknown factors, play a more
446 important role in the process of OSL sensitisation in natural conditions (**Sawakuchi et al., 2011;**
447 **Mineli et al., 2021**).

448 **OSL sensitisation and implications**

449 Variations in OSL sensitivity have also been linked to recombination processes, as shown by
450 relationships with luminescence lifetimes among different rock types (**Chithambo et al., 2007**)
451 and radiofluorescence sensitivity among rocks and sediments (**Niyonzima et al., 2020**), and an
452 anti-correlation with water content has also been reported (**Sharma et al., 2017**). Despite these
453 advances, the processes controlling OSL sensitisation after quartz is released from its parent
454 rock remains to be uncovered. In this study, the strong correlation between OSL sensitisation
455 and the concentration of $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$ centres, as well as Ti and Li trace elements, indicates that
456 Ti-Li-related defects are key controls on sensitisation during repeated irradiation and bleaching
457 cycles. Notably, only the samples containing $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$ ESR centres showed OSL sensitisation
458 with repeated cycles of dosing and bleaching in the laboratory, while those lacking these
459 centres did not, highlighting the role of $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$ in the OSL sensitisation process. Samples with
460 high blue CL emission showed increase in OSL sensitization. The blue emission has traditionally
461 been associated with the recombination of self-trapped excitons (STEs) linked to oxygen
462 vacancies in the quartz lattice (**Stevens-Kalceff 2009; Götze et al., 2021**). More recent studies,
463 indicate a strong correlation between blue CL intensity and Ti concentration in quartz, with the
464 most intense emissions often observed in Ti-rich samples (**Leeman et al., 2012; Vasyukova et**
465 **al., 2013; Drivenes et al., 2016; Götze et al., 2024; Fonseca Teixeira et al., 2024**). These $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]$
466 centres likely enhance OSL signals by acting as electron traps and reducing competition
467 from non-radiative recombination pathways, as proposed by **Constantin et al. (2025)**. The
468 presence of such defects therefore appears to be a key indicator of sensitisation potential.
469 Overall, our results emphasise that OSL sensitization by irradiation and bleaching is controlled
470 by a combination of inherited defect structures and geological processes, with Ti and Li
471 impurities playing a central role in governing luminescence behaviour in quartz.

472 **Influence of crystallisation conditions: Granite vs Volcanic equivalents**

473 The comparison between CATA G granite and AMV rhyolite tuff provides important insights into
474 the role of crystallisation conditions on defect formation and OSL sensitisation. Although both
475 samples are derived from the same magmatic system and have similar zircon crystallisation
476 ages, the quartz from the volcanic sample (AMV) exhibits significantly higher Ti and Li
477 concentrations, stronger $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$ ESR intensities, a more intense 150-200 °C TL peak, and the
478 highest laboratory OSL sensitisation potential. These differences can be attributed to

479 contrasting crystallisation conditions. Quartz in the AMV rhyolite likely formed at higher
480 temperatures (~700-900 °C) and lower pressures (~0.1-0.5 GPa), favouring increased
481 incorporation of Ti into the quartz lattice (**Wark and Watson, 2006; Thomas et al., 2010; Huang**
482 **and Audétat, 2012; Fonseca Teixeira et al., 2025**). In contrast, quartz from the CATA G-granite
483 crystallised at lower temperatures (~650–700 °C) (**Tuttle & Bowen, 1958; Luth et al., 1964;**
484 **Piwinskii, 1973**) and higher pressures (~1–2 GPa), conditions that limit Ti incorporation and
485 reduce lattice strain. Cooling rates further influence defect concentrations. The slow cooling of
486 the granite allowed for defect annealing and structural relaxation, whereas rapid cooling of the
487 rhyolitic lava led to quenching-induced defects and higher defect densities. Additionally,
488 tectonic setting plays a role: the Catalina Granite formed in the relatively stable footwall of a
489 detachment system with minimal post-emplacement deformation (**Figure S2a, b and c**), while
490 the AMV rhyolite formed in an actively extending environment, promoting additional defect
491 formation. Together, these factors explain the higher defect density and sensitisation potential
492 in volcanic quartz compared to its plutonic equivalent.

493 **Effect of metamorphism**

494 Metamorphism further modifies defect structures, as shown by the reduced Ti concentrations
495 in the DR2-metamorphosed granite compared to its undeformed counterpart (DR1). Quartz
496 recrystallisation under metamorphic conditions reduces Ti solubility and promotes diffusion,
497 leading to a decrease in Ti-related defects (**Wark and Watson, 2006; Thomas et al., 2010**). This
498 demonstrates that post-crystallisation processes can significantly alter luminescence-related
499 defect populations.

500 **ESR defect centres and role of Li impurity**

501 All samples exhibit E'_1 , peroxy, and Al-hole centres, with strong correlations between E'_1 and
502 peroxy centres ($r > 0.90$), consistent with their interpretation as Frenkel pairs (**Dave et al.,**
503 **2022; Timar-Gabor et al., 2023**). The variable intensities of E'_1 and peroxy which are likely
504 related to differences in crystallisation age, thermal history, and geological origin. The highest
505 intensities observed in the Jack Hills sample likely reflect its ancient crystallisation age,
506 suggesting that such defect centres may preserve long-term geological information.

507 A strong positive correlation between Li concentration and both the natural $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$ electron
508 centre and the saturated $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ hole centre (natural + 40 kGy) indicates that Li plays a key role
509 in the formation and stabilisation of these defect centres in quartz. This can be explained by the
510 different roles of Li^+ in Ti- and Al-related ESR defects. In Ti-related defect complex, Li^+
511 contributes to local charge balance and is structurally associated with the $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$ centre,
512 facilitating electron trapping during irradiation ($[\text{TiO}_4]^0 + e^-$ (irradiation) + $\text{Li}^+ \rightarrow [\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$
513 (electron centre)) (**Ikeya, 1993**). As a result, the intensity of this centre shows a strong
514 correlation with Li concentration at natural doses, possibly up to the range where the dose
515 response remains increasing, because at higher irradiation doses it shows a decline in the
516 concentration of this centre, which varies randomly between samples (**Woda & Wagner, 2007;**
517 **Benzid & Timar-Gabor, 2020b**).

518 In contrast, for Al-related defects, Li^+ is initially associated with the precursor complex
519 $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{Li}^+]^0$. Upon irradiation, hole trapping leads to the formation of the $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ centre and the
520 release of Li^+ to an interstitial position ($[\text{AlO}_4/\text{Li}^+]^0 + h$ (irradiation) $\rightarrow [\text{AlO}_4/h]^0$ (hole centre)
521 $+ \text{Li}^+$) (Ikeya, 1993). At high irradiation doses (natural + 40 kGy), the signal approaches
522 saturation, meaning that most precursor sites are converted into $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ centres. This leads to
523 the observed correlation between Li concentration and the saturated $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ signal.
524 The correlation between Li trace element concentrations and $[\text{TiO}_4\text{-Li}^+]^0$ ESR centre confirms
525 earlier reports (Liu et al., 2022; Tissoux et al., 2026) and supports the hypothesis that this
526 centre forms specifically through Li local charge balance. More recently, Liu et al., (2022)
527 reported that ESR intensities Ti related centres are influenced by the movement of Li^+ and H^+
528 ions with temperature, which may also explain the variations in $[\text{TiO}_4\text{-Li}^+]^0$ ESR centres observed
529 in volcanic and igneous rock samples derived from the same magma but subjected to different
530 geological processes such as AMV rhyolite tuff and CATA G granite samples in our study.
531 Furthermore, the strong correlation of Li impurity with $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ hole centre with irradiation
532 suggests that the increase in these centres is also controlled by Li impurity concentration in the
533 samples. The results highlight that Li trace elements exert a strong control on ESR signals,
534 influencing their radiation sensitivity, which is crucial for understanding ESR signals for dating
535 and provenance applications. These findings reinforce the interpretation that Li impurities
536 actively govern the production of paramagnetic defect centres during irradiation, thus playing a
537 central role in the radiation response of quartz.

538 6 Conclusions

539 The present study investigates OSL sensitisation through repeated dosing and bleaching of
540 quartz from diverse source rocks -including granites, sandstones, volcanic and metamorphic
541 rocks, as well as some derived sediments-spanning crystallisation ages from millions to billions
542 of years. Defects within the quartz were analysed using a various spectroscopic techniques,
543 including TL, OSL, ESR, SEM-CL, Raman spectroscopy and LA-ICPMS. The OSL results revealed
544 variable sensitisation behaviour among different samples. Notably, only those quartz grains
545 that exhibited the $[\text{TiO}_4\text{-Li}^+]^0$ paramagnetic centre in ESR, had notably high concentration of
546 titanium and lithium impurities and had high blue emission in SEM-CL showed OSL sensitisation
547 following repeated cycles of laboratory dosing and bleaching. The samples that sensitise had
548 significantly higher concentrations of titanium and lithium impurities, up to an order of
549 magnitude, compared to the samples that do not sensitise. A positive correlation was found
550 between the concentrations of Ti and Li (as measured by LA-ICPMS), the $[\text{TiO}_4\text{-Li}^+]^0$ centre (as
551 observed in ESR), and the degree of OSL sensitisation. Samples with higher concentrations of
552 these elements consistently showed greater levels of laboratory OSL sensitisation. Overall, our
553 results suggest that the OSL sensitisation of quartz in nature is primarily governed by the types
554 of defects inherited from the parent rock. We suggest that Ti and Li impurities, and their
555 associated paramagnetic centres, play a key role in OSL sensitisation by irradiation and light
556 exposure. The results also underscore the significant role of Li^+ ion impurities in the formation
557 of paramagnetic centres like $[\text{AlO}_4]^0$ and $[\text{TiO}_4\text{-Li}^+]^0$, thereby advancing our understanding of
558 radiation interactions with specific defects in quartz. This highlights the importance of
559 integrating defect-based analyses with luminescence measurements to improve the application
560 of OSL sensitivity as a provenance tool. Future studies should investigate whether these

561 patterns are consistent across different geological catchments and explore their manifestation
562 in sediments derived from these source rocks.

563

564

565 **Acknowledgments**

566 This study is funded by the European Research Council Consolidator Grant - PROGRESS, (ERC-
567 CoG-101043356). The views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only
568 and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council.
569 Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.
570 Support to SJM by the HUN-REN Research Centre for Astronomy and Earth Sciences (CSFK)
571 during the course of this study is appreciated.

572

573 **Open Research**

574 All relevant data is freely available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17141272>.

575 **Conflict of Interest Disclosure**

576 The authors declare there are no conflicts of interest for this manuscript.

577 **References**

- 578 Alexanderson, H. (2022). Luminescence characteristics of Scandinavian quartz, their connection
579 to bedrock provenance and influence on dating results. *Quaternary Geochronology*, 69, 101272.
580 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2022.101272>
- 581 Balintoni, I., Balica, C., Ducea, M. N., & Hann, H.-P. (2014). Peri-Gondwanan terranes in the
582 Romanian Carpathians: A review of their spatial distribution, origin, provenance, and evolution.
583 *Geoscience Frontiers*, 5(3), 395-411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsf.2013.09.002>
- 584 Basu, A. (1985). Reading provenance from detrital quartz. In G. G. Zuffa (Ed.), *Provenance of*
585 *Arenites* (NATO ASI Series, Ser. C: Mathematical and Physical Sciences, Vol. 148), Springer.
586 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-2809-6_11
- 587 Benzid, K., & Timar-Gabor, A. (2020a). Phenomenological model of aluminium-hole ($[AlO_4/h^+]^0$)
588 defect formation in sedimentary quartz upon room temperature irradiation: Electron spin
589 resonance (ESR) study. *Radiation Measurements*, 130, 106187.
590 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2019.106187>
- 591 Benzid, K., & Timar-Gabor, A. (2020b). The compensation effect (Meyer–Neldel rule) on
592 $[AlO_4/h^+]$ and $[TiO_4/M^+]$ paramagnetic centers in irradiated sedimentary quartz. *AIP Advances*,
593 10, 075114. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0005161>

- 594 Benzid, K., & Timar-Gabor, A. (2021). On the dose dependence prior and after stimulation with
595 visible light of E' and Al-hole centres in sedimentary quartz: correlation and mechanisms.
596 *Radiation Measurements*, 141, 106522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2021.106522>
- 597 Birkman, M., & Damon, P. E. (1966). K-Ar chronology of the Tucson Mountains, Pima County,
598 Arizona. *Geological Society of America Bulletin*, 77(10), 1225-1234.
599 [https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606\(1966\)77\[1225:ACOTTM\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606(1966)77[1225:ACOTTM]2.0.CO;2)
- 600 Blatt, H. (1987). Oxygen isotopes and the origin of quartz. *Journal of Sedimentary Petrology*,
601 57(2), 373-377. <https://doi.org/10.1306/212F8B34-2B24-11D7-8648000102C1865D>
- 602 Bojar, A. V., Neubauer, F., & Fritz, H. (1998). Cretaceous to Cenozoic thermal evolution of the
603 southwestern South Carpathians: Evidence from fission-track thermochronology.
604 *Tectonophysics*, 297(3-4), 229-249. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-1951\(98\)00170-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-1951(98)00170-X)
- 605 Brezeanu, D., Avram, A., Micallef, A., Cinta Pinzaru, S., & Timar-Gabor, A. (2021). Investigations
606 on the luminescence properties of quartz and feldspars extracted from loess in the Canterbury
607 Plains, New Zealand South Island. *Geochronometria*, 48(1), 46-60.
608 <https://doi.org/10.2478/geochr-2021-0005>
- 609 Brown, W. H. (1939). Tucson Mountains, an Arizona basin range type. *Geological Society of
610 America Bulletin*, 50(5), 697-760. <https://doi.org/10.1130/GSAB-50-697>
- 611 Capaldi, T. N., Rittenour, T. M., & Nelson, M. S. (2022). Downstream changes in quartz OSL
612 sensitivity in modern river sand reflect sediment source variability: Case studies from Rocky
613 Mountain and Andean rivers. *Quaternary Geochronology*, 71, 101317.
614 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2022.101317>
- 615 Caracciolo, L. (2020). Sediment generation and sediment routing systems from a quantitative
616 provenance analysis perspective: Review, application and future development. *Earth-Science
617 Reviews*, 208, 103226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2020.103226>
- 618 Chithambo, M. L., Preusser, F., Ramseyer, K., & Ogundare, F. O. (2007). Time-resolved
619 luminescence of low sensitivity quartz from crystalline rocks. *Radiation Measurements*, 42,
620 205–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2006.07.005>
- 621 Clift, P. D. (2006). Controls on the erosion of Cenozoic Asia and the flux of clastic sediment to
622 the ocean. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 241, 571–580.
623 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2005.11.028>
- 624 Constantin, D., Dave, A. K., Grecu, Ș., Kabacińska, Z., Antuzevics, A., Barla, A., Urdea, P., Ducea,
625 M. N., & Timar-Gabor, A. (2025). Tracing quartz provenance: A multi-method investigation of
626 luminescence sensitisation mechanisms of quartz from granite source rocks and derived
627 sediments. *Chemical Geology*, 683, 122774. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2025.122774>
- 628 Creasy, S. C., Banks, N. G., Ashley, R. P., & Theodore, T. G. (1977). Middle Tertiary plutonism in
629 the Santa Catalina and Tortolita Mountains, Arizona. *U. S. Geological Survey, Open-File Report*,
630 5, 705-717. <https://doi.org/10.3133/ofr76262>
- 631 Dave, A. K., Timar-Gabor, A., Kabacińska, Z., Scardia, G., Safaraliev, N., Nigmatova, S., &
632 Fitzsimmons, K. E. (2022a). A novel proxy for tracking the provenance of dust based on paired
633 E'–peroxy paramagnetic defect centres in fine-grained quartz. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 49,
634 e2022GL095007. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL095007>
- 635 del Río, I., Sawakuchi, A. O., Góes, A. M., Hollanda, M. H. B. M., Furukawa, L. Y., Porat, N., Jain,
636 M., Mineli, T. D., & Negri, F. D. A. (2021). Luminescence signals of quartz and feldspar as new
637 methods for stratigraphic discrimination and provenance analysis of siliciclastic successions:

- 638 The case of the Parnaíba Basin (Brazil) of West Gondwana. *Basin Research*, 33(3), 2938–2959.
639 <https://doi.org/10.1111/bre.12590>
- 640 Drivenes, K., Larsen, R. B., Müller, A., & Sørensen, B. E. (2016). Crystallisation and uplift path of
641 late Variscan granites evidenced by quartz chemistry and fluid inclusions: Example from the
642 Land's End granite, SW England. *Lithos*, 252–253, 57–75.
643 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lithos.2016.02.011>
- 644 Ducea, M. N., Giosan, L., Carter, A., Balica, C., Stoica, A. M., Roban, R. D., Balintoni, I., Filip, F., &
645 Petrescu, L. (2018). U–Pb detrital zircon geochronology of the lower Danube and its tributaries:
646 Implications for the geology of the Carpathians. *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems*, 19,
647 3208–3223. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GC007659>
- 648 Ducea, M. N., Triantafyllou, A., & Krcmaric, J. (2020). New timing and depth constraints for the
649 Catalina metamorphic core complex, southeast Arizona. *Tectonics*, 39(8), e2020TC006383.
650 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020TC006383>
- 651 Fonseca Teixeira, L. M., Laurent, O., Troch, J., Siddoway, C. S., Tavazzani, L., Vho, A., Burn, M.,
652 Nimis, P., Putlitz, B., Chelle-Michou, C., Anczkiewicz, R., Finger, F., Triebold, S., Putlitz, P., &
653 Lanari, P. (2024). Tracking quartz and zircon provenance in sedimentary rocks using Ti
654 distributions: Unlocking the volcanic–plutonic connection in old igneous systems. *Earth and
655 Planetary Science Letters*, 643, 118906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2024.118906>
- 656 Fayon, A. K., Peacock, S. M., Stump, E., & Reynolds, S. J. (2000). Fission track analysis of the
657 footwall of the Catalina detachment fault, Arizona: Tectonic denudation, magmatism, and
658 erosion. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 105(B5), 11,047–11,062.
659 <https://doi.org/10.1029/1999JB900421>
- 660 Fitzsimmons, K. E. (2011). An assessment of the luminescence sensitivity of Australian quartz
661 with respect to sediment history. *Geochronometria*, 38, 199–208.
662 <https://doi.org/10.2478/s13386-011-0030-9>
- 663 Fornash, K. F., Patchett, P. J., Gehrels, G. E., & Spencer, J. E. (2013). Evolution of granitoids in
664 the Catalina metamorphic core complex, southeastern Arizona: U–Pb, Nd, and Hf isotopic
665 constraints. *Contributions to Mineralogy and Petrology*, 165(6), 1295–1310.
666 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00410-013-0859-4>
- 667 Garzanti, E., Andò, S., & Vezzoli, G. (2009). Grain-size dependence of sediment composition and
668 environmental bias in provenance studies. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 277, 422–432.
669 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2008.11.007>
- 670 Gehrels, G. (2014). Detrital zircon U–Pb geochronology applied to tectonics. *Annual Review of
671 Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 42(1), 127–149. [https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-earth-050212-
672 124012](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-earth-050212-124012)
- 673 Gemignani, L., Sun, X., Braun, J., van Gerve, T. D., & Wijbrans, J. R. (2017). A new detrital mica
674 $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dating approach for provenance and exhumation of the Eastern Alps. *Tectonics*, 36(8),
675 1521–1537. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017TC004483>
- 676 Goswami, K., Panda, S. K., Alappat, L., & Chauhan, N. (2024). Luminescence for sedimentary
677 provenance quantification in river basins: A methodological advancement. *Quaternary
678 Geochronology*, 79, 101488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2023.101488>
- 679 Götze, J., Pan, Y., & Müller, A. (2021). Mineralogy and mineral chemistry of quartz: A review.
680 *Mineralogical Magazine*, 85(5), 639–664. <https://doi.org/10.1180/mgm.2021.72>

- 681 Götze, J. (2009). Chemistry, textures and physical properties of quartz: Geological
 682 interpretation and technical application. *Mineralogical Magazine*, 73(4), 645–671.
 683 <https://doi.org/10.1180/minmag.2009.073.4.645>
- 684 Götze, J., MacRae, C. M., Pan, Y., Wilson, N. C., Torpy, A., & Audétat, A. (2024). The 450 nm (2.8
 685 eV) cathodoluminescence emission in quartz and its relation to structural defects and Ti
 686 contents. *American Mineralogist*, 109(1), 122–134. <https://doi.org/10.2138/am-2022-8884>
- 687 Götze, J., Pan, Y., Stevens-Kalceff, M., Kempe, U., & Müller, A. (2015). Origin and significance of
 688 the yellow cathodoluminescence (CL) of quartz. *American Mineralogist*, 100(7), 1469–1482.
- 689 Götze, J., Plötze, M., & Habermann, D. (2001). Origin, spectral characteristics and practical
 690 applications of the cathodoluminescence (CL) of quartz – a review. *Mineralogy and Petrology*,
 691 71(3–4), 225–250. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s007100170040>
- 692 Gray, H. J., Tucker, G. E., & Mahan, S. (2016). Evaluating luminescence as a means to
 693 understand controls on sediment transport. *AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts, 2016*, EP13B-1038.
- 694 Gray, H. J., Jain, M., Sawakuchi, A. O., Mahan, S. A., & Tucker, G. E. (2019). Luminescence as a
 695 sediment tracer and provenance tool. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 57(4), 987–1017.
 696 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019RG000646>
- 697 Guild, F. N. (1905). Petrography of the Tucson Mountains, Pima County, Arizona. *American*
 698 *Journal of Science*, s4-20(118), 313–318. <https://doi.org/10.2475/ajs.s4-20.118.313>
- 699 Guzmán, G., Quinton, J. N., Nearing, M. A., Mabit, L., & Gómez, J. A. (2013). Sediment tracers in
 700 water erosion studies: Current approaches and challenges. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, 13,
 701 816–833. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-013-0659-5>
- 702 Huang, R., & Audétat, A. (2012). The titanium-in-quartz TitaniQ thermobarometer: A critical
 703 examination and re-calibration. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 84, 75–89.
 704 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gca.2012.01.009>
- 705 Ikeya, M. (1993). *New applications of electron spin resonance: Dating, dosimetry and*
 706 *microscopy* (520 pp.). Singapore: World Scientific Publishing.
- 707 Jeong, G. Y., & Choi, J. H. (2012). Variations in quartz OSL components with lithology,
 708 weathering and transportation. *Quaternary Geochronology*, 10, 320–326.
 709 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2012.02.023>
- 710 Koiter, A. J., Owens, P. N., Petticrew, E. L., & Lobb, D. A. (2013). The behavioural characteristics
 711 of sediment properties and their implications for sediment fingerprinting as an approach for
 712 identifying sediment sources in river basins. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 125, 24–42.
 713 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2013.05.009>
- 714 Krishnan, R. (1945). Raman spectrum of quartz. *Nature*, 155(3938), 452.
 715 <https://doi.org/10.1038/155452a0>
- 716 Lapp, T., Kook, M., Murray, A. S., Thomsen, K. J., Buylaert, J.-P., & Jain, M. (2015). A new
 717 luminescence detection and stimulation head for the Risø TL/OSL reader. *Radiation*
 718 *Measurements*, 81, 178–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2015.02.001>
- 719 Leeman, W. P., MacRae, C. M., Wilson, N. C., Torpy, A., Lee, C. T., Student, J. J., Thomas, J. B., &
 720 Vicenzi, E. P. (2012). A study of cathodoluminescence and trace element compositional zoning
 721 in natural quartz from volcanic rocks: Mapping titanium content in quartz. *Microscopy and*
 722 *Microanalysis*, 18(6), 1322–1341. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1431927612013426>

- 723 Li, S. H. (2002). Luminescence sensitivity changes of quartz by bleaching, annealing and UV
724 exposure. *Radiation Effects and Defects in Solids*, 157, 357–364.
725 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10420150212998>
- 726 Liu, C.-R., Ji, H., Li, W.-P., Wei, C.-Y., & Yin, G.-M. (2022). The relationship between irradiation
727 sensitivity of quartz Al and Ti centers and baking temperature by volcanic lava flow: Example of
728 Datong volcanic group, China. *Radiation Measurements*, 157, 106823.
729 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2022.106823>
- 730 Luth, W. C., Jahns, R. H., & Tuttle, O. F. (1964). The granite system at pressures of 4 to 10
731 kilobars. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 69(4), 759–773.
732 <https://doi.org/10.1029/JZ069i004p00759>
- 733 Mackey, J. M. (1963). EPR study of impurity-related color centers in germanium-doped quartz.
734 *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 39(1), 74–83. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1734035>
- 735 Mashkovtsev, R. I., & Pan, Y. (2013). Nature of paramagnetic defects in α -quartz: Progresses in
736 the first decade of the 21st century. In J. Götze & R. Möckel (Eds.), *New developments in quartz*
737 *research: Varieties, crystal chemistry and uses in technology* (pp. 65–104). New York: Nova
738 Science Publishers.
- 739 McKeever, S. W. S., Bøtter-Jensen, L., Agersnap Larsen, N., Mejdahl, V., & Poolton, N. R. J.
740 (1996). Optically stimulated luminescence sensitivity changes in quartz due to repeated use in
741 single aliquot readout: Experiments and computer simulations. *Radiation Protection Dosimetry*,
742 65, 49–54. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.rpd.a031680>
- 743 McKeever, S. W. S., Chen, C. Y., & Halliburton, L. E. (1985). Point defects and the pre-dose effect
744 in natural quartz. *Nuclear Tracks and Radiation Measurements*, 10(4–6), 489–495.
745 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0735-245X\(85\)90047-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0735-245X(85)90047-X)
- 746 Medaris, G., Jr., Ducea, M., Ghent, E. D., & Iancu, V. (2003). Conditions and timing of high-
747 pressure Variscan metamorphism in the South Carpathians, Romania. *Lithos*, 70(2–4), 141–161.
748 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0024-4937\(03\)00096-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0024-4937(03)00096-3)
- 749 Meawad, A., Murakami, K., Ohkubo, T., Kontani, O., Etoh, J., Do Thi, M., Aparicio, C., Silva, C. M.,
750 & Maruyama, I. (2025). Evaluation of radiation-induced amorphization of α -quartz in concrete
751 aggregates using Raman spectroscopy. *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, 604, 155523.
752 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2024.155523>
- 753 Mineli, T. D., Sawakuchi, A. O., Guralnik, B., Lambert, R., Jain, M., Pupim, F. N., del Rio, I.,
754 Guedes, C. C. F., & Nogueira, L. (2021). Variation of luminescence sensitivity, characteristic dose
755 and trap parameters of quartz from rocks and sediments. *Radiation Measurements*, 144,
756 106583. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2021.106583>
- 757 Mojzsis, S. J., Harrison, T. M., & Pidgeon, R. T. (2001). Oxygen-isotope evidence from ancient
758 zircons for liquid water at the Earth's surface 4,300 Myr ago. *Nature*, 409(6817), 178–181.
759 <https://doi.org/10.1038/35051557>
- 760 Morton, A. C., & Hallsworth, C. (2007). Stability of detrital heavy minerals during burial
761 diagenesis. In *Developments in Sedimentology* (Vol. 58, pp. 215–245).
- 762 Moska, P., & Murray, A. S. (2006). Stability of the quartz fast-component in insensitive samples.
763 *Radiation Measurements*, 41(7–8), 878–885. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2006.06.005>
- 764 Morana, M., Angel, R. J., Alvaro, M., & Mihailova, B. (2023). High-temperature behavior of
765 quartz-in-garnet system revealed by *in situ* Raman spectroscopy. *Physics and Chemistry of*
766 *Minerals*, 50(1), 21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00269-023-01246-5>

- 767 Negulescu, E., Săbău, G., & Massonne, H. J. (2009). Chloritoid-bearing mineral assemblages in
768 high-pressure metapelites from the Bughea Complex, Leaota Massif (South Carpathians).
769 *Journal of Petrology*, 50(1), 103–125. <https://doi.org/10.1093/petrology/egn075>
- 770 Nian, X., Zhang, W., Qiu, F., Qin, J., Wang, Z., Sun, Q., Chen, J., Chen, Z., Liu, N., 2019.
771 Luminescence characteristics of quartz from Holocene delta deposits of the Yangtze River and
772 their provenance implications. *Quaternary Geochronology* 49, 131–137.
773 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2018.04.010>
- 774 Niyonzima, P., Sawakuchi, A. O., Jain, M., Kumar, R., Minelli, T. D., del Río, I., & Pupim, F. N.
775 (2020). Radiofluorescence of quartz from rocks and sediments and its correlation with
776 thermoluminescence and optically stimulated luminescence sensitivities. *Ancient TL*, 38(1), 11–
777 20. <https://doi.org/10.26034/la.atl.2020.540>
- 778 Parida, S., Kaushal, R. K., Chauhan, N., & Singhvi, A. K. (2025). Changes in thermoluminescence
779 sensitivity of 110 °C glow peak of quartz grains from sediments of River Ganga: Observation and
780 implications. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 656, 119267.
781 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2025.119267>
- 782 Phillips, M. P. (1976). *Geology of Tumamoc Hill, Sentinel Peak and vicinity, Pima County,*
783 *Arizona*. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- 784 Pietsch, T. J., Olley, J. M., & Nanson, G. C. (2008). Fluvial transport as a natural luminescence
785 sensitiser of quartz. *Quaternary Geochronology*, 3(4), 365–376.
786 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2007.12.005>
- 787 Piwinskii, A. J. (1973). Experimental studies of granitoids from the Central and Southern Coast
788 Ranges, California. *Tschermaks Mineralogische und Petrographische Mitteilungen*, 20(2), 107–
789 130. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01081387>
- 790 Preusser, F., Chithambo, M. L., Götte, T., Martini, M., Ramseyer, K., Sendezera, E. J., Susino, G.
791 J., & Wintle, A. G. (2009). Quartz as a natural luminescence dosimeter. *Earth-Science Reviews*,
792 97(1–4), 184–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2009.09.006>
- 793 Ramseyer, K., Baumann, J., Matter, A., & Mullis, J. (1988). Cathodoluminescence colours of α -
794 quartz. *Mineralogical Magazine*, 52(368), 669–677.
795 <https://doi.org/10.1180/minmag.1988.052.368.11>
- 796 Reiners, P. W. (2005). Zircon (U-Th)/He thermochronometry. *Reviews in Mineralogy and*
797 *Geochemistry*, 58(1), 151–179. <https://doi.org/10.2138/rmg.2005.58.6>
- 798 Reynard, B., & Zhong, X. (2023). Quartz under stress: Raman calibration and applications of
799 metamorphic inclusions to geobarometry. *Solid Earth*, 14(2), 591–602.
800 <https://doi.org/10.5194/se-14-591-2023>
- 801 Rossel, P., Oliveros, V., Ducea, M. N., Charrier, R., Scaillet, S., Retamal, L., & Figueroa, O. (2013).
802 The Early Andean subduction system as an analog to island arcs: Evidence from across-arc
803 geochemical variations in northern Chile. *Lithos*, 179, 211–230.
804 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lithos.2013.08.014>
- 805 Săndulescu, M. (1984), *Geotectonica României*, Editura Tehnică, Bucharest
- 806 Sawakuchi, A. O., Jain, M., Mineli, T. D., Nogueira, L., Bertassoli, D. J., Jr., Häggi, C., Sawakuchi,
807 H. O., Pupim, F. N., Grohmann, C. H., Chiessi, C. M., Zabel, M., Mulitza, S., Mazoca, C. E. M., &
808 Cunha, D. F. (2018). Luminescence of quartz and feldspar fingerprints provenance and
809 correlates with the source area denudation in the Amazon River basin. *Earth and Planetary*
810 *Science Letters*, 492, 152–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EPSL.2018.04.006>

- 811 Sawakuchi, A. O., Blair, M. W., DeWitt, R., Faleiros, F. M., Hyppolito, T., & Guedes, C. C. F.
812 (2011). Thermal history versus sedimentary history: OSL sensitivity of quartz grains extracted
813 from rocks and sediments. *Quaternary Geochronology*, 6(2), 261–272.
814 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2010.11.002>
- 815 Sharma, S. K., Chawla, S., Sastry, M. D., Gaonkar, M., Mane, S., Balaram, V., & Singhvi, A. K.
816 (2017). Understanding the reasons for variations in luminescence sensitivity of natural quartz
817 using spectroscopic and chemical studies. *Proceedings of the Indian National Science Academy*,
818 83, 645–653. <https://doi.org/10.16943/ptinsa/2017/49024>
- 819 Sittner, J., & Götze, J. (2018). Cathodoluminescence (CL) characteristics of quartz from different
820 metamorphic rocks within the Kaoko Belt (Namibia). *Minerals*, 8(5), 190.
821 <https://doi.org/10.3390/min8050190>
- 822 Skuja, L., Ollier, N., & Kajihara, K. (2020). Luminescence of non-bridging oxygen hole centers as
823 a marker of particle irradiation of α -quartz. *Radiation Measurements*, 135, 106373.
824 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2020.106373>
- 825 Stevens-Kalceff, M. A. (2009). Cathodoluminescence microcharacterization of point defects in
826 α -quartz. *Mineralogical Magazine*, 73(4), 585–606.
827 <https://doi.org/10.1180/minmag.2009.073.4.585>
- 828 Tanski, N. M., Rittenour, T. M., Pavano, F., Pazzaglia, F., Mills, J., Corbett, L. B., & Bierman, P.
829 (2024). Quartz luminescence sensitivity enhanced by residence time in the critical zone.
830 *Quaternary Geochronology*, 84, 101613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2024.101613>
- 831 Thomas, J. B., Watson, E. B., Spear, F. S., Shemella, P. T., Nayak, S. K., & Lanzirotti, A. (2010).
832 TitaniQ under pressure: The effect of pressure and temperature on the solubility of Ti in quartz.
833 *Contributions to Mineralogy and Petrology*, 160(5), 743–759. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s00410-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00410-010-0505-3)
834 [010-0505-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00410-010-0505-3)
- 835 Timar-Gabor, A., Kabacińska, Z., Constantin, D., Dave, A. K., & Buylaert, J.-P. (2023).
836 Reconstructing dust provenance from quartz optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and
837 electron spin resonance (ESR) signals: Preliminary results on loess from around the world.
838 *Radiation Physics and Chemistry*, 212, 111138.
839 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radphyschem.2023.111138>
- 840 Tissoux, H., Rizza, M., Aupart, C., Rixhon, G., Valla, P. G., Boulay, M., Lach, P., & Voinchet, P.
841 (2026). Exploring the relationships between electron spin resonance (ESR)/luminescence
842 (OSL/TL) properties and trace element composition from quartz in various bedrocks
843 (Strengbach catchment, Vosges). *Geochronology*, 8, 37–61. [https://doi.org/10.5194/gchron-8-](https://doi.org/10.5194/gchron-8-37-2026)
844 [37-2026](https://doi.org/10.5194/gchron-8-37-2026)
- 845 Toyoda, S., Nagashima, K., & Yamamoto, Y. (2016). ESR signals in quartz: Applications to
846 provenance research – A review. *Quaternary International*, 397, 258–266.
847 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2015.05.048>
- 848 Tuttle, O. F., & Bowen, N. L. (1958). Origin of granite in the light of experimental studies in the
849 system $\text{NaAlSi}_3\text{O}_8$ – KAlSi_3O_8 – SiO_2 – H_2O . *Geological Society of America Memoir* 74, 1–146.
850 <https://doi.org/10.1130/MEM74-p1>
- 851 Vasyukova, O. V., Goemann, K., Kamenetsky, V. S., MacRae, C. M., & Wilson, N. C. (2013).
852 Cathodoluminescence properties of quartz eyes from porphyry-type deposits: Implications for
853 the origin of quartz. *American Mineralogist*, 98(1), 98–109.
854 <https://doi.org/10.2138/am.2013.4018>

- 855 Wark, D. A., & Watson, E. B. (2006). TitaniQ: A titanium-in-quartz geothermometer.
856 *Contributions to Mineralogy and Petrology*, 152(6), 743–754. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s00410-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00410-006-0132-1)
857 [006-0132-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00410-006-0132-1)
- 858 Weil, J. A. (2000). A demi-century of magnetic defects in alpha-quartz. In G. Pacchioni, L. Skuja,
859 & D. L. Griscom (Eds.), *Defects in SiO₂ and related dielectrics: Science and technology* (pp. 91–
860 109). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-010-0944-7_6
- 861 Wilde, S. A., Valley, J. W., Peck, W. H., & Graham, C. M. (2001). Evidence from detrital zircons
862 for the existence of continental crust and oceans on the Earth 4.4 Gyr ago. *Nature*, 409(6817),
863 175–178. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35051550>
- 864 Woda, C., & Wagner, G. A. (2007). Non-monotonic dose dependence of the Ge- and Ti-centres
865 in quartz. *Radiation Measurements*, 42(9), 1441–1452.
866 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2007.06.018>
- 867 Woodhead, J., Hellstrom, J., Hergt, J., Greig, A., & Maas, R. (2007). Isotopic and elemental
868 imaging of geological materials by laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass
869 spectrometry. *Geostandards and Geoanalytical Research*, 31(4), 331–343.
870 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-908X.2007.00104.x>
- 871 Zhang, J., Li, S. H., Sun, J., Tongyan, L., Zhou, X., & Hao, Q. (2023). Quartz luminescence
872 sensitivity variation in the Chinese loess deposits: The potential role of wildfires. *Journal of*
873 *Quaternary Science*, 38, 49–60. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.3462>

874 **Table 1.** Sample locations, types of rocks and their Zircon U-Pb crystallisation and Apatite cooling ages.

875

Samples	Location	Latitude, Longitude	Type	Ages	References
AMV	Arizona (USA)	32.210 N 110.992 W	Volcanic	26-28 Ma	Bikerman and Damon, 1966
CATA G	Arizona (USA)	32.4405 N 110.8602 W	Granite	Zircon U-Pb crystallisation age: 25 to 27 Ma	Creasy et al., 1977; Ducea et al., 2020
CATA- SED MND	Arizona (USA)	32.444 N 110.892 W	Sediment	Apatite fission track age: 21 to 24 Ma	
ORACLE	Arizona (USA)	32.624 N 110.75 W	Granite	Zircon U-Pb crystallisation age: ~1.4 Ga; Apatite fission track age: ~20-23 Ma	Fayon et al., 2000 ; Fornash et al., 2013
JH9902	Jack Hills, Narryer Gneiss Complex, Western Australia	26.184 S 116.967 E	Sandstone and conglomerate	Detrital zircons with U- Pb crystallisation age up to ca. 4.38 Ga. Deposited ca. 3.2-3.3 Ga	Mojzsis et al., 2001
DR1	Romania	45.340 N 25.162 E	Granite	Zircon U-Pb crystallisation age: 460- 480 Ma, Metamorphism- 360 to 320 Ma	Medaris Jr et al., 2003 ; Negulescu et al., 2009
DR2	Romania	45.340 N 25.162 E	Metamorphic Granite		
RATG 22- 06	Romania	45.375 N 22.873 E	Granite	Zircon U-Pb age: 310 ±5 Ma	Bojar et al., 1998 ; Balintoni et al., 2014
RATG 22- 03	Romania	45.408 N 22.886 E	Sediment		

876

877 **Figure 1.** OSL decay curves of all investigated samples after irradiation with 100 Gy beta dose and
 878 preheat to 220 °C for 10 s. Data for CATA G, CATA-SED MND, RATG 22-03 and RATG22-06
 879 samples is from Constantin et al. (2025).

880

881 **Figure 2.** Laboratory sensitisation measurements for all samples: a) Samples AMV-rhyolite, ORACLE-
 882 granite, CATA G-granite and CATA-SED MND-sediment showed an increase in sensitisation and b)
 883 samples JH9902-sandstone, DR1-granite, DR2-metamorphosed granite, RATG 22-06-granite and
 884 RATG 22-03-sediment showed no increase in sensitisation with repeated cycles of dosing and
 885 bleaching. The average of data from three aliquots is shown and the error bars are the standard
 886 errors.

887

888 **Figure 3.** ESR intensities for natural a) E'_1 , b) peroxy, c) Al-hole $[AlO_4]^0$, and d) $[TiO_4^-Li^+]^0$
 889 paramagnetic centres. All intensities were determined from peak-to-peak amplitudes and are
 890 normalized to a sample mass of 100 mg. E'_1 and peroxy signals were measured at room temperature,
 891 while Al-hole and Ti-Li signals were measured at 90 K. The error bars are standard error in the data.
 892 Samples below the dotted line show OSL sensitisation, whereas those above do not.

893

894 **Figure 4.** SEM-CL spectra for all samples. a) Samples AMV-rhyolite, ORACLE-granite, CATA G-granite
 895 and CATA-SED MND-sediment showed higher intensities of blue emission and b) samples JH9902-
 896 sandstone, DR1-granite, DR2-metamorphosed granite, RATG 22-06-granite and RATG 22-03-
 897 sediment showed very little blue emission. SEM-CL data is average of nine spectra from three
 898 different grains and error bars are standard error of the mean values. Please note that same scale
 899 for Y-axis is used.

900

901 **Figure 5.** Trace element concentrations from LA-ICPMS a) Lithium, b) Titanium, c) Aluminium and d)
 902 Germanium for all sample. The error bars are standard error of the mean. Samples below the dotted
 903 line show OSL sensitisation, whereas those above do not.

904

905 **Figure 6.** Average Raman spectra of a selection of quartz samples, acquired using 785 nm laser
 906 excitation. Spectral range is 100 - 1200 cm^{-1} . Dashed lines indicate the positions of main peaks.

907

908 **Figure 7.** Correlations between the maximum degree of sensitisation and: a) $[TiO_4^-Li^+]^0$ centre, b)
 909 $[AlO_4]^0$ centre for natural + 40 kGy from ESR, c) Li impurity and d) Ti impurity concentrations from
 910 LA-ICPMS. The maximum degree of OSL sensitisation is defined as the ratio between the highest OSL
 911 signal ($L_{x,max}$) and the OSL signal obtained in the first cycle (L_1) of the laboratory sensitisation
 912 experiment. The error bars are standard error in the data.

913

914 **Figure 8.** Correlation of Li trace element concentration with (a) $[TiO_4^-Li^+]^0$ ESR intensity at the natural
 915 dose, and (b) $[AlO_4]^0$ ESR intensity for natural + 40 kGy. For the $[TiO_4^-Li^+]^0$ centre, ESR intensities
 916 measured at the natural dose were used for correlation as decline in the intensity of the centre has
 917 been reported at high doses (**Woda & Wagner 2007; Benzid & Timar-Gabor 2020b**). For the $[AlO_4]^0$
 918 centre, ESR intensities at high irradiation doses (natural + 40 kGy) are used, since this signal usually
 919 saturates at such doses and thus reflects the total concentration of Al-hole centres.

920

921

922

923

924

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

26 per scan. The E'_1 signal intensity was quantified as the peak-to-peak height of the spectrum
27 centred at $g = 2.006$ (Dave et al. 2022).

28 Peroxy spectra were obtained at room temperature using the following settings: scanned
29 magnetic field of 3350 ± 200 G, modulation amplitude of 1 G, modulation frequency of 100 kHz,
30 microwave power of 2 mW, conversion time of 50 ms, and time constant of 40 ms. The signal
31 amplitude was measured using peak-to-peak height from $g = 2.009$ to $g = 2.003$ (Odom & Rink
32 1989).

33 The ESR signals of the Al-hole and Ti centres were recorded at 90 K. The Al-hole centre was
34 measured using a modulation amplitude of 0.1 mT, scanned magnetic field of 3350 ± 150 G,
35 sweep time of 120 s, and microwave power of 2 mW. The Al-hole signal was quantified as peak-
36 to-peak height between $g = 2.018$ and $g = 1.993$ (Toyoda and Falguères, 2003). Each value
37 represents an average of three measurements, with the sample rotated by 120° between each
38 scan.

39 For Ti centre measurements, the magnetic field was scanned between 3490 ± 110 G with a
40 modulation amplitude of 1 G, modulation frequency of 100 kHz, microwave power of 10.02 mW,
41 conversion time of 10 ms, and a time constant of 20.48 ms. All results are average over three
42 measurements, with the sample rotated by 120° between each, and each measurement
43 consisting of 10 averaged scans. Baseline correction of the Ti spectra was performed using
44 Bruker's Xenon software with a polynomial function (1st or 2nd order, occasionally higher as
45 needed). Background correction regions were ~ 3410 – 3460 G and ~ 3530 – 3600 G. Ti signal
46 intensities were calculated from the peak at $g = 1.979$ to the trough near $g = 1.913$ – 1.915 (Duval
47 et al. 2015). All ESR measurements were carried out within weeks to months following gamma
48 irradiation.

49 **Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS)**

50 Quartz grain morphology, surface texture, and topography were examined using scanning
51 electron microscopy (SEM) with secondary electron (SE) detection, employing an Everhart-
52 Thornley detector. SE imaging was carried out at an accelerating voltage of 2–5 kV with a 60 μm
53 aperture in high current mode, producing beam currents of 550–700 pA (measured using a
54 Faraday cup) (Figure S3) and a working distance (WD) of 8.5 mm. Following grain selection, Energy
55 Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) mapping was performed to confirm quartz composition. Elemental
56 data for O, Si, Al, Ti, Fe, Mg, and K, along with overall spectra, were collected simultaneously to
57 detect any inclusions or compositional anomalies. EDS mapping was conducted at 15 kV, with a
58 60 μm aperture in high current mode, using a working distance of 8.5 mm, a dwell time of 100
59 μs , 32 frames, and a resolution of 256×200 pixels. This analysis provided a comprehensive
60 overview of grain purity (Figure S4) and helped identify suitable areas for subsequent
61 Cathodoluminescence (CL) analysis.

62 **Cathodoluminescence (CL) analysis**

63 CL spectroscopy was the final stage of our study and it employed an accelerating voltage (EHT) of
64 15 kV and a 60 μm aperture in high current mode (1.3 nA beam current) in order to ensure
65 sufficient electron interaction and luminescence signal. A 300 lines/mm grating provided a
66 balance between spectral resolution and sensitivity across a broad wavelength range (341 to 758
67 nm). The slit width was set to 3.2 mm to achieve sufficient signal intensity, yielding a spectral
68 resolution of 0.32 nm/channel. The CL spectra were captured at 10 s exposure time. The beam
69 was blanked after each acquisition to further limit damage. CL spectra were captured at a central
70 wavelength of 550 nm. For each sample, three zones from three different grains were analysed
71 (totalling nine spots per sample), allowing for representative and consistent data across multiple
72 regions of each grain.

Supplementary material

Sample	E' (a.u.)	E' nat + 40 kGy (a.u.)	Peroxy nat (a.u.)	Peroxy nat + 40 kGy (a.u.)	[AlO ₄] ⁰ nat (a.u.)	[AlO ₄] ⁰ nat + 40 kGy (a.u.)	[TiO ₄ Li ⁺] ⁰ natural (a.u.)	[TiO ₄ Li ⁺] ⁰ nat+ 40 kGy (a.u.)
Samples for which OSL signal gets sensitised								
AMV	0.01 ± 0	0.013 ± 0.001	0.146 ± 0.011	0.17 ± 0.007	1.688 ± 0.03	40.382 ± 0.777	7.163 ± 0.145	2.59 ± 0.014
CATA G	0.015 ± 0.004	0.014 ± 0	0.078 ± 0.017	0.128 ± 0.001	1.729 ± 0.063	14.438 ± 0.126	2.506 ± 0.171	0.928 ± 0.004
CATA- SED MND	0.019 ± 0.001	0.015 ± 0.001	0.141 ± 0.011	0.143 ± 0.004	1.205 ± 0.045	22.04 ± 0.348	0.926 ± 0.026	1.528 ± 0.07
ORACLE	0.042 ± 0.002	0.075 ± 0.002	0.345 ± 0.014	0.219 ± 0.01	1.034 ± 0.028	15.448 ± 0.441	2.589 ± 0.025	4.216 ± 0.091
Samples for which OSL do not get sensitised								
JH9902	0.182 ± 0.002	0.285 ± 0.008	0.789 ± 0.021	0.723 ± 0.032	2.173 ± 0.233	3.129 ± 0.057	Not detected	Not detected
DR1	0.016 ± 0.001	0.035 ± 0.001	0.073 ± 0.003	0.051 ± 0.002	0.394 ± 0.005	0.777 ± 0.004	Not detected	Not detected
DR2	0.027 ± 0.001	0.039 ± 0.001	0.218 ± 0.001	0.173 ± 0.003	0.504 ± 0.013	1.409 ± 0.004	Not detected	Not detected
RATG 22-06	0.02 ± 0.001	0.024 ± 0	0.127 ± 0.005	0.115 ± 0.001	0.923 ± 0.017	1.246 ± 0.011	Not detected	Not detected
RATG 22-03	0.045 ± 0.005	Not measured	0.15 ± 0.004	Not measured	1.092 ± 0.043	Not measured	Not detected	Not measured

73

74 **Table S2.** ESR results of all samples with natural and natural plus 40000 Gy dose. Each sample was measured for three different
75 angles to maintain the homogeneity. E' and peroxy were measured at room temperature and [AlO₄]⁰ and [TiO₄Li⁺]⁰ signals were
76 measured at 90 K. The ESR intensities presented are mass normalised (100 mg).

Samples	Li-7 (ppm)	Al-27 (ppm)	Ti-49 (ppm)	Ge-74 (ppm)
Samples for which OSL got sensitised				
AMV	16.71 ± 0.19	54.20 ± 0.62	108.82 ± 1.10	0.64 ± 0.02
CATA G	8.23 ± 0.53	52.09 ± 1.32	52.30 ± 0.91	0.60 ± 0.03
CATA-SED MND	10.77 ± 0.14	63.08 ± 0.93	45.71 ± 0.75	0.79 ± 0.02
ORACLE	11.05 ± 0.16	116.70 ± 1.48	99.35 ± 1.15	1.23 ± 0.02
Samples for which OSL did not get sensitised				
JH9902	0.29 ± 0.06	21.71 ± 0.65	3.34 ± 0.20	1.08 ± 0.02
DR1	1.28 ± 0.08	199.09 ± 2.85	60.78 ± 0.76	1.30 ± 0.03
DR2	2.72 ± 0.11	94.68 ± 4.51	5.95 ± 0.53	0.40 ± 0.03
RATG 22-06	0.46 ± 0.23	29.46 ± 2.38	9.30 ± 0.75	0.50 ± 0.04
RATG 22-03	0.93 ± 0.09	7.84 ± 0.31	8.31 ± 0.26	0.84 ± 0.02

77

78 **Table S3:** Weighted averages of Titanium, Lithium, Aluminium and Germanium concentration
79 from LA-ICPMS for all samples.

Supplementary material

Samples	Degree of sensitisation (max L_x/L_1)
AMV	7.447 ± 0.54
CATA G	4.8 ± 0.621
CATA-SED MND	3.425 ± 0.674
ORACLE	3.814 ± 0.547
JH9902	1.029 ± 0.005
DR1	1.137 ± 0.052
DR2	1.163 ± 0.201
RATG 22-06	1.148 ± 0.092
RATG 22-03	1.27 ± 0.032

80

81 **Table S4:** Values of degree of sensitisation for all samples. The degree of sensitisation is the ratio
 82 of the maximum OSL signal ($L_{x, \max}$) to the signal from the first cycle (L_1) of the laboratory
 83 sensitisation experiment.

85

86

Figure S1. Geological maps of all sampling locations: (a) samples from southeast Arizona, USA (AMV, CATA G, CATA-SED MND, and ORACLE), modified after **Terrien (2012)**; (b) samples from the Southern Carpathians, Romania (DR1 and DR2), base map is from Geological Map of Romania (1:200,000); (c) samples from the Retezat Mountains, Romania (RATG22-06 and RATG22-03), modified after **Constantin et al. (2025)**; and (d). samples from Jack Hills, Australia (JH9902). In this map, the JH992 locality (shown in a red rectangle) corresponds to the JH9902 sample, map modified after **Mojzsis et al. (2001)**.

87

88

89 **Figure S2.** Plane polar (a) and crossed polar (b) microscopic views of Catalina granite (CATA G)
90 showing the leucocratic nature. White slightly “dirty” altered feldspars and clean looking quartz.
91 Opaque is magnetite. Field of view is 1.5 cm diagonal. (c) Plane polar view of biotite and
92 magnetite in granite. Field of view is 0.5 mm diagonal. (d) Plane polar view of AMV rhyolite tuff
93 with elongated fiamme in the central part of photograph and (e) crossed polars view of rhyolite
94 tuff with phenocrystals of plagioclase (twinned) and quartz (white crystal in the centre of view).
95 Field of view 1.5 cm diagonal.

96

97

Supplementary material

98

99

100

Figure S3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of multiple quartz grains extracted from all samples.

101

102 **Figure S4.** The SEM-EDS overlay elemental maps of field of view (secondary electrons image), Si
103 and Al in the investigated quartz samples.

104

Supplementary material

105 **Figure S5.** Average thermoluminescence glow curves after 100 Gy of beta dose using 3 to 5
 106 aliquots per sample. The grey uncertainty bars represent the standard error of the mean. Heating
 107 rate is 5 °C/s. Prior to the measurement natural TL read-out up to 500 °C has been carried out on
 108 the same aliquot.

109

110

111 **Figure S6.** ESR spectra of the natural dose and natural + 40000 Gy dose a) E'_1 , b) peroxy, c) $[AlO_4]^0$,
 112 and d) $[TiO_4Li^{+0}]$ paramagnetic centres for samples for which OSL signal sensitised.

113

114 **Figure S7.** ESR spectra of the natural dose and natural + 40000 Gy a) E'_1 , b) peroxy, c) $[AlO_4]^0$, and
 115 d) $[TiO_4Li^+]^0$ paramagnetic centres for samples for which OSL did not sensitise.

116

117

Supplementary material

118 **Figure S8.** Correlation between E_1' and peroxy from ESR measurements a) for natural dose and
 119 b) high irradiation doses (i.e., Natural + 40 kGy) for all samples.

Supplementary material

120 **Figure S9.** Results of Lorentzian deconvolution of quartz Raman spectra, showing the band
 121 position shifts at 126, 204 and 464 cm⁻¹, along with their corresponding intensities and full width
 122 at half maximum (FWHM). All parameters are presented with associated error bars represented
 123 as standard error.

124

125 **Figure S10.** Correlation of Ti impurity with natural $[\text{TiO}_4\text{Li}^+]^0$ ESR intensity.

Supplementary material

126 **Script S1: Python script for Raman data analysis**

```
127 import os
128 import numpy as np
129 from scipy.optimize import curve_fit
130 from scipy.interpolate import interp1d
131 from sklearn.metrics import r2_score
132 from scipy.signal import find_peaks
133 import pybaselines as pb
134 from scipy.ndimage import gaussian_filter
135
136 path_file = []
137
138
139 def Anscombe_Transfomration(y):
140
141     y = np.array(y)
142
143     def anscombe_transform(data):
144         return 2.0 * np.sqrt(data + 3 / 8)
145
146     def inverse_anscombe_transform(transformed_data):
147         return ((transformed_data / 2.0) ** 2) - 3 / 8
148
149     transformed_y = anscombe_transform(y)
150     smoothed_transformed_y = gaussian_filter(transformed_y, sigma=2)
151     denoised_y = inverse_anscombe_transform(smoothed_transformed_y)
152
153     return denoised_y
154
155
156 def IASLS(y):
157
158     bas = pb.whittaker.iasls(y, lam=200)[0]
159
160     return y - bas
161
162
163 def lorentzian(x, position, intensity, width):
164     return intensity * (width / 2) ** 2 / ((x - position) ** 2 + (width /
165 2) ** 2)
166
167 def lorentzian_fit(x, *params):
168     peaks = len(params) // 3
169     y = np.zeros_like(x)
170     for i in range(peaks):
171         center = params[i * 3]
172         intensity = params[i * 3 + 1]
173         width = params[i * 3 + 2]
174         y += lorentzian(x, center, intensity, width)
175     return y
176
177 def read_text_file(file_path):
178     with open(file_path, 'r') as f:
```

Supplementary material

```
179         f.read()
180
181     for name in range(len(path_file)):
182
183         path = path_file[name]
184
185         os.chdir(path)
186
187         for file in os.listdir():
188             if file.endswith(".txt"):
189                 file_path = f"{path}\\{file}"
190                 read_text_file(file_path)
191                 file1 = np.loadtxt(file_path, dtype=float)
192
193                 condition = (file1[:, 0] >= 100) & (file1[:, 0] <= 1200)
194                 X, Y = file1[condition, 0], file1[condition, 1]
195
196                 original_y = Y
197
198                 Y = Anscombe_Transfomration(Y)
199                 Y = IASLS(Y)
200
201                 if len(Y) > 0:
202
203                     Y = Y / max(Y)
204
205                     initial_dif = abs(X[1] - X[0])
206
207                     imp = 1
208                     f = interp1d(X, Y)
209                     newXspec = np.linspace(X[0], X[-1], round(imp * len(X)))
210                     newYspec = f(newXspec)
211
212                     neg_bound_int, pos_bound_int = 0, 1 * max(Y)
213                     neg_bound_pos, pos_bound_pos = min(X), max(X)
214                     neg_bound_wid, pos_bound_wid = 0, max(X) - min(X)
215
216                     Y_res = np.mean(np.abs(np.gradient(Y)))
217                     X_res = 3
218
219                     for wid in range(0, 1):
220
221                         peaks = np.array(find_peaks(Y, height=0, prominence=1
222 * Y_res, width=wid)[0])
223
224                         int1 = len(peaks)
225
226                         initial_guess = []
227
228                         bound1 = []
229                         bound2 = []
230
231                         for i21 in range(int1):
232                             if Y[peaks[i21]] > 0:
```

Supplementary material

```
233         initial_guess.append(X[peaks[i21]])
234         initial_guess.append(Y[peaks[i21]])
235         initial_guess.append(initial_dif)
236
237         bound1.append(X[peaks[i21]] - X_res *
238 initial_dif)
239         bound1.append(Y[peaks[i21]] - Y_res / 4)
240         bound1.append(neg_bound_wid)
241
242         bound2.append(X[peaks[i21]] + X_res *
243 initial_dif)
244         bound2.append(Y[peaks[i21]])
245         bound2.append(pos_bound_wid)
246
247         params, _ = curve_fit(lorentzian_fit, X, Y,
248 p0=initial_guess, maxfev=pow(10, 10), bounds=(bound1, bound2))
249
250         y_pred = lorentzian_fit(X, *params)
251
252         residual_y = Y - y_pred
253
254         peaks2 = np.array(find_peaks(residual_y, height=0,
255 prominence=1 * Y_res)[0])
256
257         peaks3 = np.concatenate((peaks, peaks2))
258
259         peaks4 = [round(peaks3[0])]
260
261         for i in range(1, len(peaks3)):
262             if abs(peaks3[i] - peaks4[-1]) >= X_res:
263                 peaks4.append(round(peaks3[i]))
264
265         peaks3 = peaks4
266
267         initial_guess = []
268
269         bound1 = []
270         bound2 = []
271
272
273         for i21 in range(len(peaks3)):
274             if Y[peaks3[i21]] > 0:
275                 initial_guess.append(X[peaks3[i21]])
276                 initial_guess.append(Y[peaks3[i21]])
277                 initial_guess.append(initial_dif)
278
279             bound1.append(X[peaks3[i21]] - X_res *
280 initial_dif)
281             bound1.append(0)
282             bound1.append(neg_bound_wid)
283
284             bound2.append(X[peaks3[i21]] + X_res *
285 initial_dif)
286             bound2.append(max(Y))
```

Supplementary material

```
287         bound2.append(pos_bound_wid)
288
289         params2, _ = curve_fit(lorentzian_fit, newXspec,
290 newYspec, p0=initial_guess, maxfev=pow(10, 10), bounds=(bound1, bound2))
291
292         parameter = []
293         rezultate = []
294
295         position_array = []
296
297         for int in range(0, len(params2), 3):
298
299             condition = []
300
301             if all(condition):
302                 parameter.append([params2[int], params2[int +
303 1], params2[int + 2]])
304
305                 peak_area = np.pi * params2[int + 1] *
306 params2[int + 2] / 2
307
308                 position_array.append(params2[int])
309
310                 rezultate.append([params2[int], params2[int +
311 1], params2[int + 2], peak_area, lorentzian_fit(newXspec, *[params2[int],
312 params2[int + 1], params2[int + 2]])])
313
314                 parameter = sorted(parameter, key=lambda x: x[0],
315 reverse=False)
316                 parameter = np.concatenate((parameter))
317                 y_pred = lorentzian_fit(newXspec, *parameter)
318
319                 position_array = np.array(sorted(position_array))
320
321                 rezultate = sorted(rezultate, key=lambda x: x[0],
322 reverse=True)
323                 r2 = r2_score(newYspec, y_pred)
324
325                 if len(rezultate) > 0:
326
327                     print('R2 = ', r2)
328
329                     for nr2 in range(len(rezultate)):
330                         if rezultate[nr2][1] > 0 and 0 < rezultate[nr2][0]
331 < 2000 and rezultate[nr2][2] < 50:
332                             print(round(rezultate[nr2][0], 3),
333                                   '\t I = ', round(rezultate[nr2][1], 3),
334                                   '\t A = ', round(rezultate[nr2][3], 3),
335                                   '\t W = ', round(rezultate[nr2][2], 3))
336
337                 print()
338
```

339 **References**

- 340 Constantin, D., Dave, A. K., Grecu, Ş., Kabacińska, Z., Antuzevics, A., Barla, A., Urdea, P.,
341 Ducea, M. N., & Timar-Gabor, A. (2025). Tracing quartz provenance: A multi-method
342 investigation of luminescence sensitisation mechanisms of quartz from granite source rocks
343 and derived sediments. *Chemical Geology*, 683, 122774.
344 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2025.122774>
- 345 Dave, A. K., Timar-Gabor, A., Kabacińska, Z., Scardia, G., Safaraliev, N., Nigmatova, S., &
346 Fitzsimmons, K. E. (2022). A novel proxy for tracking the provenance of dust based on paired
347 E'–peroxy paramagnetic defect centers in fine-grained quartz. *Geophysical Research Letters*,
348 49(e2022GL095007), e2022GL095007. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL095007>
- 349 Duller, G. A. T. (2003). Distinguishing quartz and feldspar in single grain luminescence
350 measurements. *Radiation Measurements*, 37(2), 161–165. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487(02)00170-1)
351 [4487\(02\)00170-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487(02)00170-1)
- 352 Duval, M., & Guilarte, V. (2015). ESR dosimetry of optically bleached quartz grains extracted
353 from Plio-Quaternary sediment: Evaluating some key aspects of the ESR signals associated
354 to the Ti-centers. *Radiation Measurements*, 78, 28–41.
355 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2014.10.002>
- 356 Geological map of Romania 1:200000. Geological Institute of Romania, Spatial geological
357 data. <https://geoportal.igr.ro/viewgeol200k>
- 358 Mojzsis, S. J., Harrison, T. M., & Pidgeon, R. T. (2001). Oxygen-isotope evidence from ancient
359 zircons for liquid water at the Earth's surface 4,300 Myr ago. *Nature*, 409(6817), 178–181.
360 <https://doi.org/10.1038/35051557>
- 361 Odom, A. L., & Rink, W. J. (1988). Natural accumulation of Schottky-Frenkel defects:
362 Implications for a quartz geochronometer. *Geology*, 17(1), 55–58.
363 [https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613\(1988\)017<0055:NAOSFD>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613(1988)017<0055:NAOSFD>2.3.CO;2)
- 364 Terrien, J. J., 2012. The role of magmatism in the Catalina metamorphic core complex,
365 Arizona: insights from integrated thermochronology, gravity and aeromagnetic data
366 (Doctoral dissertation, Syracuse University).
- 367 Toyoda, S., & Falguères, C. (2003). The method to represent the ESR signal intensity of the
368 aluminum hole center in quartz for the purpose of dating. *Advances in ESR Applications*, 20,
369 7–10.
- 370